

Two-stage Line Planning with Infrastructure Restrictions

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Abstract

Two-stage line planning with uncertain infrastructure restrictions allows to develop a set of line plans, which offers on the one hand a good and cheap offer in the undisturbed state and on the other hand adapts itself optimally to possible infrastructure restrictions. To reduce differences between the first-stage line plan and the scenario-dependent line plans of the second stage, replanning costs are introduced. Considering travel times, line operation costs, and replanning costs, a set of line plans is searched, optimally combining the diverging goals. The results reveal that the consideration of future restrictions while determining the first stage line plans leads to substantial improvement for the entire system. At the same time, however, the computing time is on average two to five times longer.

Zweistufige Linienplanung mit Infrastrukturbeschränkungen

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Zusammenfassung

Zweistufige Linienplanung unter ungewissen Infrastruktureinschränkungen ermöglicht es, ein Set an Linienplänen zu entwickeln, welches ein gutes und günstiges Angebot im ungestörten Zustand bietet und auf der anderen Seite sich optimal an die gegebenen Einschränkungen anpassen kann. Um die Unterschiede des Linienplans der ersten Stufe und den szenarienabhängigen Linienplänen der zweiten Stufe so gering wie möglich zu halten, werden Umplanungskosten eingeführt. Unter Berücksichtigung der Reisezeitkosten, den Betriebskosten der Linien und der Umplanungskosten wird ein Set an Linienplänen gesucht, welche diese sich gegebenenfalls widersprechenden Ziele optimal verbindet. Es zeigt sich, dass die Berücksichtigung der zukünftigen Einschränkungen bei der Erstellung des Linienplans der ersten Stufe je nach Parameterauswahl deutliche Verbesserungen für das Gesamtsystem bringen kann. Gleichzeitig ist aber auch eine im Durchschnitt zwei bis fünf Mal längere Rechenzeit in Kauf zu nehmen.

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Figure 1: Declaration of originality

Contents

Contents	5
List of Figures	8
List of Tables	9
1 Introduction	11
2 Literature Review	13
2.1 Line Planning Problem	13
2.2 Stochastic Programming	13
2.3 The Concept of Robustness in Stochastic Programming	14
2.4 Robustness in Line Planning	14
2.5 Stochastic Programming in Public Transportation	15
2.6 Stochastic Programming for the Line Planning Problem	16
3 Research Gap and Aim of the Thesis	17
4 Methods	18
4.1 Line Planning Problem	18
4.2 Two Stage Line Planning Problem	18
4.2.1 Replanning Strategies	18
4.2.2 Solving Procedures	19
4.2.3 Constraint formulation	19
4.3 Libraries and Solvers	19
4.3.1 Solving Techniques and Solvers	19
4.4 Network Infrastructure	20
4.4.1 Second-stage Scenarios	21
4.5 Demand model	21
4.6 Line Generation	21
4.7 Elimination of Sublines	23
4.8 Parameters to control the optimization behavior	24
4.9 Composition of the Two-Stage Line Planning Problem	24
4.10 Introduction to the Notation	24
4.11 Passenger Routing	25
4.12 Line Routing	26
4.12.1 Line origin-destination variable absolute value constraint	27
4.12.2 Line origin-destination variable number constraint	28
4.12.3 Line branch constraint	28

4.13	Frequency assignment	28
4.13.1	Predefined Lines	28
4.13.2	Direct multiplication	29
4.13.3	Linearization	29
4.13.4	Line groups	29
4.14	Line and Flow Aggregation	30
4.14.1	Flow aggregation constraint	30
4.14.2	Line aggregation constraint	31
4.15	Capacity constraints	31
4.15.1	Vehicle capacity constraint	31
4.15.2	Infrastructure capacity constraint	31
4.16	Subtour Elimination	31
4.16.1	Upper and lower bound for the secondary line origin-destination variable	32
4.16.2	Different options to solve the subtour elimination problem	34
4.17	Variables in two-stage modeling	35
4.18	Difference constraints	36
4.18.1	Line difference constraints	36
4.18.2	Frequency difference constraints	37
4.18.3	Passenger path difference constraints	37
4.19	Replanning Constraints	38
4.19.1	Line rerouting determination constraint	38
4.19.2	Line replanning allowance constraint	38
4.19.3	Replanning budget	38
4.20	Objective Value	39
4.20.1	Objective value function without replanning costs	39
4.20.2	Objective value function with replanning costs	39
5	Results	41
5.1	Weighted Travel and Line Cost	41
5.2	Number of lines	43
5.2.1	General Overview	44
5.2.2	Network with 18 Nodes	45
5.3	Replanning Budget	46
5.4	Replanning costs	50
5.5	Different restrictions	53
5.5.1	Standard Scenarios	54
5.5.2	Peripheral Restricted Scenarios	54
5.5.3	Heavy Restricted Scenarios	55
5.5.4	Combined Scenarios	56

5.5.5	Optimization parameters	56
5.6	Equal Network Capacity, Various Frequencies	59
5.7	First Stage or Second Stage Undisturbed Scenario	61
5.8	Various Probabilities of the Undisturbed Second-Stage Scenario	62
5.9	Passenger Path Replanning Costs	63
5.10	Line Optimization	65
5.11	Computational performance	66
5.12	Solving Performance	68
5.13	Performance of Various Procedures, Solvers and Settings	69
5.13.1	Relative Speed of Various Procedures and Solvers	70
5.13.2	Iterative solving heuristic	71
5.13.3	Relative Speed of Various Settings	72
6	Discussion	74
6.1	The Significance of the Composition of the Objective Value Function	74
6.1.1	Replanning Costs as Part of the Objective Value	74
6.2	Networks, Scenarios, and the Line Pool	75
6.3	Optimality Gap	75
6.4	Robustness in Two-Stage Line Planning	76
7	Conclusion	78
8	Outlook	80
9	Appendix	81
9.1	Declaration of the use of generative AI	81
9.2	List of Abbreviations	81
9.2.1	Parameters	81
9.2.2	Constants	81
9.2.3	Variables	82
9.2.4	Sets	82
9.2.5	Indices	82
	References	83

List of Figures

1	Declaration of originality	4
2	SiouxFalls with OD demand	21
3	Line Plan	22
4	Line Plan legend	22
5	Line with a subline	23
6	Line with a subline and the secondary lines	23
7	Passenger origin-destination vector	25
8	Passenger path matrix	25
9	Passenger path matrix, first row marked with blue	25
10	Passenger path matrix, first column marked with yellow	25
11	Passenger od vector 1	26
12	Passenger od vector 2	26
13	Sum of all passenger od vectors for the same origin node	26
14	Passenger path 1	30
15	Passenger path 2	30
16	Aggregated passenger paths	30
17	Line od list	32
18	Line path matrix	32
19	Secondary line 1	32
20	Secondary line 2 with destination node 2	32
21	Secondary line 3 with destination node 3	32
22	Secondary line 4	32
23	Secondary line 2 with destination node 2	35
24	Secondary line 3 with destination node 3	35
25	Summed secondary lines	35
26	Weighted travel and line cost, cost plot 1	42
27	Weighted travel and line cost, cost plot 2	43
28	Costs of different line numbers	44
29	Costs of different line numbers	45
30	Costs of different line numbers	46
31	Line plan with 18 nodes and 14 lines	47
32	Replanning budget, cost plot 1	48
33	Replanning budget, cost plot 2	49
34	Line plan, 14 nodes, 18 lines	50
35	Replanning cost, cost plot 1	51
36	Replanning cost, cost plot 2	52
37	Replanning cost, replanning plot	53

38	Line plan with peripheral restrictions	54
39	Line plan with heavy restrictions	55
40	Various restrictions, cost plot 1	57
41	Various restrictions, cost plot 2	58
42	Various restrictions, replanning plot	59
43	Frequency and capacity, cost and utilization plot 1	60
44	Frequency and capacity, cost plot 2	61
45	Various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario, cost plot 1	62
46	Various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario, cost plot 2	63
47	Passenger path replanning costs, cost plot 1	64
48	Passenger path replanning costs, replannings plot	65
49	Computational performance for different sets of nodes and lines	67
50	Gurobi solving process	69
51	Relative computational effort of procedures and solvers	70
52	Relative computational effort of various settings	73

List of Tables

1	Composition of the Line Planning Problem	24
2	Upper and lower bound of the secondary line od variable	33
3	Utilization of variables in the two stages	36
4	Optimization parameters for different weights	42
5	Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets	44
6	Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets	47
7	Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets	50
8	Scenario probabilities	56
9	Optimization parameters for different frequencies and vehicle capacities	56
10	Optimization parameters for different frequencies and vehicle capacities	60
11	Optimization parameters for various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario	62
12	Optimization parameters for various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario	64
13	Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets	66
14	Cost and calculation time difference between the integrated and separated procedure (the total costs for the separated procedure are higher)	68
15	Relative computational effort of various procedures and solvers	70
16	Relative computational effort of various settings	72
17	Abbreviations and their explanations (parameters)	81
18	Abbreviations and their explanations (constants)	81

19 Abbreviations and their explanations (variables) no repetition of variable 82
20 Abbreviations and their explanations (indexes) 82
21 Abbreviations and their explanations (indexes) 82

1 Introduction

The provision of a good and reliable public transportation system is crucial for a modern economy and society (Buchanan 2019). To ensure the quality as well as the constant development and improvement of these systems, a planning process was set up by the planning bodies as well as the scientific community (Liebchen 2008). This planning system consists of a multi-stage planning process, at the end of which the plan for a transport service is drawn up. It consists of network planning, line planning, timetable planning, rotation planning, and shift planning (Liebchen 2008). During network planning, the infrastructure to be provided is determined based on demand forecasts (Schnieder 2015). Since network infrastructure elements are designed for long periods, are expensive, and can only be realized with a long lead time, infrastructure planning is intended for the very long term. This means that the built infrastructure can only be adapted to general trends and need to provide enough capacity and flexibility to deal with short-term fluctuation (Gilrein et al. 2021).

Network planning is followed by line planning, which intends to develop a line plan, suitable for the given infrastructure. The number, the paths, and the stopping pattern of the lines are determined. The stopping pattern influences not only the speed of transportation but also the coverage of the line along the route. Additionally, the frequency of the line is specified, which determines the transportation capacity of the line (Reinhardt 2012) and (Borndörfer et al. 2007). It is much easier to change the path and especially the frequency of lines compared with the infrastructure mentioned above.

The third step is timetable planning. This determines the time at which the vehicles run on the line. While the infrastructure requirements are considered rather on a macroscopic level during line planning, the feasibility of the line and timetable planning must be demonstrated as part of the timetable planning. This is done by taking a detailed look at the infrastructural conditions (number of tracks, nodes, crossing conflicts, safety elements) (Reinhardt 2012).

The next steps are rotation planning and shift planning, which will not be discussed in detail here, as they belong to the short-term planning cycle and are only very limited connected to the line planning problem.

The entire planning process from network planning to service planning is still mainly carried out manually and in separate steps (Liebchen 2008). In some countries, however, iterative processing between network planning, line planning, and timetable planning has increasingly been observed for several decades (SMA and Partner et al. 2022), (Federal office for transport 2015). Technical aids such as simulations and optimization algorithms are also increasingly being used (Unterberger et al. 2022). With the ongoing spread of more powerful computers and better algorithms, computer-aided methods for line planning are now moving from research into practice (Unterberger et al. 2022).

Optimization algorithms are particularly suitable for line planning (Borndörfer et al. 2007). Such algorithms optimize an objective function along predefined boundaries, the so-called con-

straints. In the case of the line planning problem, for example, the costs for the operator or the travel times for the users can be minimized. The constraints typically include the requirements for the transportation of all passengers and the consideration of vehicle and line capacities (Borndörfer et al. 2007).

Optimization algorithms aim to solve a problem optimally based on fixed initial conditions. In transportation planning, however, initial conditions are uncertain, be it the demand for transportation services or the availability of routes (Pu et al. 2021). To better take such uncertainties into account, optimization algorithms can be adapted so that the results are more robust against deviations from the assumed state. However, it is also possible to extend the concept of robustness to scenario individual planning, which is done using stochastic mathematical optimization (Pu et al. 2021). First, the classic optimization problem is solved. Then an event occurs, for example, the interruption of a line. This results in different scenarios, each with a pre-defined probability. In the second stage, these scenarios will be optimized, resulting in different optimal line plans. The allowed difference between these line plans may be determined. This thesis will be discussing these aspects, using a two-stage optimization approach to solve the line planning problem under uncertain infrastructure conditions.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Line Planning Problem

The one-stage line planning problem is a well-discussed approach to use mathematical optimization to create optimal line plans. There are several different approaches to the line planning problem including cost-oriented models, passenger-oriented models, game-theoretic models, location-based models, and various heuristics (Schöbel 2012). The most used approach in literature is the passenger-oriented model, where two sub-approaches may be differentiated, the direct traveler approach and the minimization of traveling time approach. The direct travelers approach has the goal to maximize the number of people, who can travel directly from their origin to their destination using one line. The first implementations were proposed by Dienst H 1978 and Bussieck 1998. Adding constraints for lower and upper frequencies of lines as well as capacity constraints lead to the revised direct travelers approach. Extensive techniques for finding an optimal solution as well as a software package were provided by Bussieck 1998. Further research showed that it is possible to adapt the line planning problem in a way, that the travel time of all passengers is minimized. To ensure, that there is not one line per origin-destination pair to provide direct service, a budget constraint or a multi-objective optimization both considering the travel time costs and the line operation costs is necessary (Schöbel 2012). There are two approaches on how to model the passenger routing along the network as well as the determination of the best lines. One approach, the so-called system split, is fixing the passenger routes first and then in the second step determining the best lines and their frequencies (Borndörfer et al. 2007). The advantage of this approach is the computational speed when solving the problem, the main disadvantage is, that passengers usually adapt their behavior based on the offered service. Thus the optimization result of this approach may not always be optimal. Borndörfer et al. 2008 proposed as well an integral line planning problem, combining the passenger routing and line determination in the same optimization process. He showed that these problems are indeed NP-hard to solve Borndörfer et al. 2008.

2.2 Stochastic Programming

Stochastic programming is an extension of classical, deterministic optimization problems. However, most real-world problems involve some sort of uncertainty. To deal with this kind of problem, it is either possible to determine the uncertain variables with the best available knowledge or to solve the optimization problem for all possible parameter combinations (Shapiro et al. 2007). Another approach is to use stochastic programming. Often probability distributions are known beforehand. Stochastic programming takes these probability distributions into account when solving optimization problems (Shapiro et al. 2007). One example of an unknown variable is the demand for a specific time frame. Using historical data, it is often possible to determine the probability distributions. Stochastic programming may be applied in the specific

form of two-stage programs (Shapiro et al. 2007). In these problems, a decision maker has to decide on a policy, not knowing the random outcome of some processes happening between the first and second stage. After the materialization of the random outcome, a second decision has to be taken, considering the outcome. The two-stage model assumes several possible outcomes, each with a certain probability. Stochastic programming has a long history and was first proposed by George Dantzig in 1955 (Infanger 2011). Numerous publications in a wide range of applications followed, proving the wide applicability of stochastic programming (Infanger 2011). Stochastic programming is applied in various contexts, such as climate change mitigation, fleet management, investment decisions, insurance policies, electricity generation, and risk management (Wallace et al. 2005).

2.3 The Concept of Robustness in Stochastic Programming

Robustness is an essential concept in stochastic programming and more specifically in two-stage modeling approaches. The authors of an overview paper on robustness propose several different concepts of robustness (Goerigk et al. 2016). The most conservative approach is strict robustness, which searches for a solution, which is doable for every possible scenario. A less conservative approach is cardinality-constrained robustness, which limits the parameters, which simultaneously may assume their worst-case values. To relax the requirements even further, light robustness is proposed, which requires a minimal quality of the nominal solution and then searches among the set of solutions meeting the quality standard for the most robust one. Another approach is regret robustness, which minimizes the difference to the objective function of the best solution that would have been possible in a scenario, instead of minimizing the worst-case performance of a solution. Robustness is also applied in two-stage optimization approaches. Here adjustable robustness and recoverable robustness become relevant. Adjustable robustness is the direct application of two-stage optimization. The values for the here-and-now variables have to be determined by the optimization algorithm in advance, whereas the wait-and-see variables wait until the actual scenario becomes known. Slightly different from the adjustable robustness is the recoverable robustness, which allows for adaptations and recovery measures in case of previously unknown disturbances.

2.4 Robustness in Line Planning

Several works examined the concept of robustness for line planning, combining it with infrastructure restrictions such as *Á. Marín et al. 2009* and *Bessas et al. 2011*. The first paper includes an additional element in the objective function, the price of robustness. This price consists either of longer travel times or extra costs for operators in case of disruptions. The authors propose a heuristic for line replannings in case of disruptions (*Á. Marín et al. 2009*). The second paper uses various line pools with different utility functions per line pool. After capacity reductions in the network, some adaptations to the line plan are applied, either using

the same line pool or a different line pool. The adaptations are found using an iterative, heuristic algorithm (Bessas et al. 2011).

2.5 Stochastic Programming in Public Transportation

Stochastic Programming was applied in numerous fields within public transportation. The applications span from time table planning (Hassannayebi et al. 2017) and (Michel et al. 2016) and vehicle scheduling (Naumann et al. 2011) to origin-destination demand determination (Sun et al. 2024) among many others.

The paper from Hassannayebi et al. 2017 uses a two-stage approach to model the timetable planning problem. In the first stage, the departure and arrival times of the trains are set as the decision variables and thus optimized by the algorithm. Afterward, the uncertainty in the form of passenger flows is included in the model. In the second stage, the departure and arrival times are altered and the frequency of the lines may be adapted to better fit the passenger flows and to prevent under-capacity. Additionally, the concept of robust stochastic programming, first proposed by Mulvey et al. 1995, was used to find solution sets that are very close to each other. Specifically, the cost variance is added to the objective function. This reduces differences between the scenarios and thus increases the robustness.

The second paper, which deals with a two-stage approach for timetabling, is from Michel et al. 2016. This paper uses as well a two-stage approach to optimize the transfer times of the passengers. In the first stage, a decision variable for each line is introduced, which allows offsetting the line within some bounds. The first stage is then optimized to minimize the total transfer time for the passengers. In the second stage, some random variables are introduced: deviations from arrival times, deviations from departure time, and deviations from the number of transferring people. Using different realizations of these random variables, the total waiting time is minimized. The goal here is to find the best offset values for a robust timetable with the shortest transfer times, even if there are deviations in terms of passengers' travel and dwelling times.

In contrast to the previous papers, which focused on timetable planning, the paper of Naumann et al. 2011 focuses on vehicle scheduling in bus networks. Vehicle scheduling is often made for undisturbed timetables. This simplification doesn't reflect the delays which often occur on bus networks. According to the work, these delays often lead to not optimal vehicle assignment. The authors now propose to include a set of scenarios with different delays throughout the bus lines and the day. Using all these scenarios, a robust vehicle schedule is developed. The objective function not only includes the cost function but also the delay costs, which are included as a quadratic term, to increase the penalty over proportionality for high delays. The authors could prove, that the stochastic approach may indeed reduce the total costs compared to a deterministic model with buffer times.

The origin-destination demand estimation is not directly part of the transport planning

cycle, but the availability of demand data is crucial for a successful outcome of the planning cycle. Therefore scientists around Sun et al. 2024 proposed to use stochastic programming to estimate demand data. A two-stage approach is used to take into account the uncertainties coming from actual traffic flows. In detail, the first stage aims to estimate the demand data using historical information. In the second stage, a set of realizations of traffic flows are taken into account. The passenger demand estimation algorithm tries to minimize the deviations from the initial demand estimation compared with the actual traffic flows. Using this approach, the authors may use historical data as well as actual realizations of traffic flows to find the best set of passenger demand to fit the realizations. The authors showed, that the efficiency and the accuracy of the proposed method is promising and leads to better results than deterministic optimization.

2.6 Stochastic Programming for the Line Planning Problem

In contrast to the one-stage line planning problem (LPP) and to stochastic optimization in timetable planning, there is only one paper, that deals with line planning-related problems with uncertain infrastructure restrictions, that uses two-stage optimization. This paper is written by Pu et al. 2021. The authors in this paper propose to use a two-stage approach to solve the line planning problem under demand uncertainty. In the first stage, nominal demand data is used to determine an optimal line plan. The line plan consists of three elements: the line path, the number of stops, and the frequency. For the second stage, different realizations of travel demand are considered to optimize a set of line plans, each with the best fit for the demand data provided. The line plans may be adapted in terms of path, number of stops, and frequency. The objective value minimizes the line operation cost and the passenger travel cost, in the first stage for the nominal line plan, and in the second stage to make the rescheduled line plan feasible. To solve the two-stage problem, the authors argue against an integral model, as the solution includes multiple line planning problems, of which each is NP-hard (Lin et al. 2014). Therefore a Lagrangian relaxation is introduced, which decouples the second-stage problem from the first-stage problem and adds the linking constraints as a Lagrangian multiplier to the objective value function. To solve two-stage problems in public transport, this approach was proposed as well by Liu et al. 2020. After the successful relaxation, the authors showed, that real-life problems may be solved with relatively low computational effort satisfyingly. Concretely, a route with 18 stations may be solved within an hour to a gap of less than 5%.

The authors of the two other papers introduced above (Á. Marín et al. 2009 and Bessas et al. 2011) don't use a proper two-stage design for their approaches. They also don't include direct replanning costs.

3 Research Gap and Aim of the Thesis

Considering the various literature about the line planning problem as well as stochastic programming in public transportation and more specifically in solving the LPP, the research gap is apparent. While passenger demand uncertainty is covered numerous times in different applications within timetable planning and once within line planning, modeling uncertain infrastructure restrictions is much less common. Specifically, no research literature was found to integrate the line planning problem with infrastructure restrictions in a two-stage approach using the concept of replanning costs, even though it was proposed by Schöbel 2012.

Taking into account the literature analysis, the field of the two-stage line planning problem with uncertain infrastructure restrictions seems promising. Therefore the thesis aims to find out whether stochastic optimization can contribute to solving line planning problems (LPP) with infrastructure restrictions and if this approach is suitable to find robust first-stage and second-stage line plans. In the first step, a flexible one-stage line problem model should be developed. In the second step, the one-stage model is extended to a two-stage problem, taking into account a set of stochastic infrastructure restrictions. Using this model, a set of parameters and scenarios are tested and evaluated. The goal is to determine the influence of different modeling approaches, infrastructure restriction sets, and modeling parameters on the computational performance as well as on the resulting line plan and the calculated costs. One major question is to determine the advantage of knowing the possible infrastructure outcomes beforehand. If the outcome is known beforehand, it is called an integrated procedure, otherwise a separated procedure. Additionally, it should be investigated, in which way the found line plan is robust and which concept of robustness fits best for the two-stage model proposed within this thesis.

All this leads to the following research questions.

- RQ 1: How can stochastic mathematical optimization be used in the context of the LPP?
- RQ 2: What performance can stochastic mathematical optimization achieve when solving an integrated two-stage LPP compared to a separated two-stage LPP?
- RQ 3: How do model parameters influence the solution and the performance of the two-stage LPP?
- RQ 4: Which solution results from the use of stochastic mathematical optimization in the context of an LPP for networks?
- RQ 5: How robust to disturbances are the line plans found by the two-stage optimization?

4 Methods

4.1 Line Planning Problem

The objective of the line planning problem (LPP) is to determine an optimal line plan for a certain route network. A line plan consists of the line paths, the stopping pattern, and the frequency of the lines, as described by Schöbel 2012. The aim during optimization is to find a line network that is as cost-effective as possible. The costs are composed of the travel time costs of the passengers and the line operation costs of the operator.

Two processes run in parallel when optimizing LPP. On the one hand, the shortest available routes are sought for passengers from their origin to their destination. This routing is mapped in the flow constraints. On the other hand, a selection of optimal lines is made from the line pool, and their optimal frequencies are determined. This process is mapped in the line constraints. Routing and line selection are linked via the capacity constraint, which ensures that the lines provide sufficient capacity for all passengers. Since the two processes run in parallel and influence each other, it can be guaranteed that the best result is found, optimally combining the two possibly conflicting objectives.

4.2 Two Stage Line Planning Problem

The two-stage line planning problem complements the basic problem with changes in infrastructure conditions that potentially require an adjustment of the line plan. Specifically, the undisturbed line planning problem is solved in the first stage. Afterwards, adjustments are made to the route network. This can be a reduction in capacity or even a closure of some edges. Different scenarios with different infrastructure restrictions can be created. Each scenario comes into effect with a certain probability. The line planning problem is then solved a second time with the new restrictions for each scenario individually, resulting in a line plan for each scenario.

4.2.1 Replanning Strategies

After solving the first stage and infrastructure restrictions becoming relevant, adaptations to the line plan have to be made. Therefore three strategies are implemented to account for the needed changes. The strategies are passenger travel path changes, line frequency changes, and line path changes. Travel path and line frequency changes are always allowed, whereas line path changes are only allowed if a line is affected by a closed edge. Travel path changes are generally for free, but it is possible to allocate costs to the passenger path changes as well. The line frequency changes and line path changes however always have a cost assigned. This cost may either counted towards the objective function or deducted from a replanning budget. In general line path changes are more expensive compared with frequency changes, but the cost may be set individually.

4.2.2 Solving Procedures

The first and second stages may either be solved at the same time or after each other. If the two-stage LPP is solved separately, no information about the second-stage restrictions is provided in the first stage, which means that the first-stage line plan is just optimal for the undisturbed condition. However, if the two stages are solved together, the possible restrictions and their probabilities are already known during the optimization of the first-stage line plan, thus providing incentives to adapt the first-stage line plan to better fit the needs of the second-stage line plan. This is called integrated procedure.

4.2.3 Constraint formulation

The formulation of the LPP constraints for this thesis follows loosely the path-based formulation proposed by Borndörfer et al. 2008. The formulations are adapted to fit the needs of the two-stage line planning problem with replanning of lines and frequencies. The constraints are described in detail in subsection 4.9.

4.3 Libraries and Solvers

For this thesis, the programming language Julia was chosen due to its simple coding and higher speed compared to Python (Pykes 2022). The constraints and objective value functions are written using the library JuMP, a library for mathematical optimization in Julia (Lubin et al. 2023).

4.3.1 Solving Techniques and Solvers

As discussed in the literature analysis, the two-stage line planning problem consists of several np-hard subproblems, which makes it very difficult to find solutions for big networks (Lin et al. 2014). As this problem is not only relevant for LPP but for a broad range of stochastic optimization problems, several different solving techniques were developed. The classical way is to use a state-of-the-art solver such as Gurobi, CPLEX, or GLPK to solve the problem. The two-stage line planning problem is a mixed integer linear or quadratic program (MILP or MIQP), depending on the choice of parameters. For details, please refer to subsection 4.13.

Lagrangian Relaxation Applying two-stage optimization, the constraints, that link the first and second stage, are the ones, which make the model typically difficult to solve. A Lagrangian Relaxation is proposed in literature to relax these constraints and to add a term to the objective function to replace these constraints, the so-called Lagrangian multiplier (A. Marín et al. 1999). This approach allows to solve the first-stage problem and the second-stage problems without hard constraints linking them. The penalty term in the objective function ensures that

the subproblems are still linked. This approach was used by Pu et al. 2021 to model a two-stage LPP.

Progressive Hedging Very similar to the Lagrangian Relaxation is the progressive hedging algorithm, which was developed by Rockafellar et al. 1991. This algorithm disassembles the initial problem into several subproblems, which are easier to solve independently. The subproblems are then solved and compared to the first stage problem. Difference variables are introduced, which act as penalty terms in the objective function to reach iteratively a solution state that is equal or similar to the solution, which would have been found when solving the whole problem as one. This algorithm was applied for two-stage optimization problems by Bashiri et al. 2021. Both Lagrangian relaxation and progressive hedging use a classic solver to solve the subproblems.

L-shaped Algorithm Another approach is the L-shaped algorithm to solve two-stage optimization problems, as done by Grass et al. 2020. It is based on the Benders decomposition technique and decouples the first-stage problem from the second-stage problems similar to the Lagrangian Relaxation algorithm. After solving the first-stage and second-stage problems, it is checked, if the subproblems adhere to the constraints of the first-stage problem. If not, bender cuts are generated and added to the first stage problem, and then everything is solved again. This procedure is repeated as long as an optimal solution is not found.

Stochastic Programs The progressive hedging algorithm as well as the L-shaped algorithm is integrated into the library Stochastic Programs written by Biel et al. 2022. Therefore Stochastic Programs was used to solve the LPP using the more advanced techniques. Stochastic Programs uses a dedicated approach to model two-stage problems.

Solver The solver Gurobi was chosen to solve all test series (Gurobi Optimization 2024). However minor tests using GLPK and HiGHS were executed as well to compare the performance (Oki 2012), (Huangfu et al. 2018)

4.4 Network Infrastructure

As a source for the infrastructure and the origin-destination matrices, Lintim was chosen, which was developed by Schöbel et al. 2022. Lintim provides several different networks for various needs. As the two-stage optimization is very resource-intensive, only small networks were used as a base. Therefore, the Sioux Falls network with 24 nodes was chosen. As computing performance is highly dependent on the number of nodes and lines, there was a need to reduce the number of nodes even further in some cases. Therefore, it is possible to use an inclusion list, which may reduce the number of nodes to as few as seven. In figure (2) the network as well as the origin-destination demand is visible, provided by Lintim.

Figure 2: Sioux Falls with OD demand

4.4.1 Second-stage Scenarios

Each optimization run consists of an undisturbed first stage and a disturbed second stage. The second stage in turn consists of several scenarios, each coming with a set of infrastructure restrictions. Additionally, each scenario has a deterministic probability, that it occurs. This probability signifies a weight of the scenario in the objective value.

4.5 Demand model

In contrast to the approach proposed by Pu et al. 2021 with an uncertain demand, the demand of this model is constant for all scenarios and given by Schöbel et al. 2022 in the Lintim framework. It is assumed in this work, that passenger demand is fixed, even if restrictions occur, which may alter travel times.

4.6 Line Generation

There are two possibilities for how lines are generated and dealt with within the LPP.

Line Pool The less complex way is to pass a list of lines to the solver. This list contains the node sequence of each line and is created manually. Each line is part of a line group, in which each line has the same frequency. This allows to link the frequencies of a line that runs in both directions. For the Sioux Falls scenario, which is used for all examples in this report, a line pool containing 28 lines and 14 line groups was created. The line pool was built to cover all nodes with at least one line, to have more lines at edges, which are used more, and to have a diverse coverage of lines throughout the network. To control the number of lines provided to

the solver, it is possible to choose the number of lines picked from the list. Lines may only be picked from the list if they are not cut in half by omitted edges. The line pool plan 3 as well as the line numbers 4 may be found below.

Figure 3: Line Plan

Figure 4: Line Plan legend

Theoretically, it would be possible to create this list with some sort of line pool generator, but the question of what constitutes a good line pool is difficult to answer, as shown by Gattermann et al. 2017, and is not a main research question within this thesis, and thus is omitted.

Line Optimization The second variant is the so-called line optimization approach. If this approach is applied, a maximum number of allowed lines is set. For these lines, the origin and destination points are determined by the optimization algorithm, and then a route along the network is found. In parallel, the passengers are routed, and the frequency of the lines is defined. As there are many more possible outcomes with this variant, the calculation time is possibly longer.

4.7 Elimination of Sublines

If the number of lines during the optimization is restricted or only a small number of lines is allowed for rerouting, the lines tend to create so-called sublines, as visible in figure 5. These sublines are problematic as they allow for unrealistic and better solutions, such as introducing a second line, even if a line is only rerouted. Often sublines are cheaper compared to a single line serving all the nodes.

Figure 5: Line with a subline

Figure 6: Line with a subline and the secondary lines

There are several subtour elimination approaches described in the literature (Oencan et al.

2009). The implementation used for this thesis loosely follows the formulation proposed by Gavish and Graves (Oencan et al. 2009). The idea is to introduce additional secondary lines, which start at the origin of the origin of the line and connect to each intermediate node of the original line, as shown in figure 5. These secondary lines must all be part of the original line, thus omitting secondary lines. The problem with this approach is its variable and constraint-intensive implementation. The technical implementation is described in detail in chapter 4.16.

4.8 Parameters to control the optimization behavior

There are some additional numerical parameters, which determine the result of the optimization process. These include the number of **allowed lines**, the **maximum frequency** of each line, the **vehicle capacity**, the **cost of replanning the frequency** as well as the **cost of replanning the line path**. Furthermore, there is a budget for line planning purposes. If this is negative, the replanning costs are added to the objective function. If it is positive, the replanning costs may be as high as the budget and are not part of the objective function. To control the importance of the travel times and the line operation costs, there is a **weight** to determine the influence of these two costs in the objective value function.

4.9 Composition of the Two-Stage Line Planning Problem

As the second-stage line planning problem consists of several subproblems, which share parts of the constraint blocks, keeping track of the constraint use in the two stages is important. Therefore, the following table gives an overview of which constraint block is used in which stage. The subsequent chapters explain all the constraint blocks in detail.

Constraint block	Ref.	First stage	First stage line opt.	Second stage
Passenger routing	4.11	yes	yes	yes
Line routing	4.12	no	for all lines	for replanned lines
Frequency assignment	4.13	linear	quadratic/linear	quadratic/linear
Line and flow aggr.	4.14	yes	yes	yes
Capacity constraints	4.15	yes	yes	yes
Subtour elimination	4.16	no	for all lines	for replanned lines
Difference det.	4.18	no	no	yes
Replanning	4.19	no	no	yes
Objective value	4.20	separated procedure	only indirectly	yes

Table 1: Composition of the Line Planning Problem

4.10 Introduction to the Notation

The notation for all variables, sets, constants, parameters, and indices is introduced where it is first used. However, some parameters play a crucial role throughout the report and are therefore introduced here.

- n is the number of stations in the network.
- V is the set of stations.
- K is the set of lines.

For an overview of all parameters, constants, variables, and indices used, refer to 9.2.1

4.11 Passenger Routing

Passenger routing is a central aspect of a line planning problem. The number of passengers for each origin-destination pair is given. For each origin-destination pair, the path with the shortest travel time through the network is searched for during optimization, taking into account the capacities provided by the lines. Specifically, a so-called passenger origin-destination list, in which the origin and destination are stored, and a matrix, in which the path from the origin to the destination is determined, are set up for each origin-destination (od) pair. This process is illustrated by a small example. Given an od pair from node 1 to node 4, represented by the vector in figure 7.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 7: Passenger origin-destination vector

The values in this vector represent the sum of all outgoing flows minus all incoming flows for each node. The passenger path matrix will now assume such values during optimization so that this condition is fulfilled. Such a passenger path matrix can be seen in figure 8.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 8: Passenger path matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 9: Passenger path matrix, first row marked with blue

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 10: Passenger path matrix, first column marked with yellow

In figures 9 and 10, the first row of the middle matrix is marked blue, and the first column of the right matrix is marked yellow. If the sum of the blue row is calculated and subtracted from the sum of the yellow column, the value 1 is obtained for the first node, which corresponds to the value for node 1 in the passenger od vector. The same procedure is used for nodes 2 to

4. Numerous alternatives for a path from node 1 to node 4 are conceivable, all of these variants are therefore permissible, provided they fulfill the equilibrium condition and the values given by the passenger od vector. If more than one passenger is going from node 1 to node 4, the sum of the departing minus the arriving flow in the origin node is equal to the positive amount of passengers. For the destination node, the sum of the departing minus the arriving flow is equal to the negative amount of all passengers. This enables the routing of several passengers parallel on potentially different routes along the network.

When solving a line planning problem, several passenger relations are usually modeled. A passenger path matrix for each origin-destination pair is created and stored in the so-called flow variable F . Similarly, the passenger od vector for each od pair is stored in another list. This list is referred to below as the passenger origin-destination list P . To make the problem smaller and thus faster, it is possible, to route all people departing from the same node in the same passenger path matrix. All od vectors, which have their origin at the same node (11 and 12) are summed and stored in an aggregated vector (13).

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 11: Passenger od vector 1

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ -2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 12: Passenger od vector 2

$$\begin{bmatrix} 3 \\ 0 \\ -2 \\ -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 13: Sum of all passenger od vectors for the same origin node

With this summarizing approach, the number of passenger path matrices is reduced from the number of od relations to the number of nodes (one passenger path matrix per origin node).

Flow conservation constraint

$$\sum_{j \in V} F_{h,i,j} - \sum_{j \in V} F_{h,j,i} = P_{h,i} \quad \forall h \in V, i \in V \quad (1)$$

- The flow variable has the value range $F \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V \times V}$.
- The passenger od list has the value range $P \in \mathbb{Z}^{V \times V}$.

4.12 Line Routing

Line routing is done similarly to passenger routing. Here too, a matrix is used to describe the path of the line, and a list is used to describe the origin and destination of this line. A list is used, to be processed directly without otherwise necessary adaptations. However, there are some deviations to the passenger routing block which will be discussed here. If the line optimization

option is selected during parameter selection, the lines are created and optimized as part of the optimization. In this case, however, it is unclear at the start of the optimization from which origin to which destination the lines will run. Therefore, a new variable is introduced, the line od variable O . This variable contains a list for each line in which the origin and destination are defined during optimization. However, to ensure that lines run from an origin to a destination, it is specified that each line od list must contain a 1 and a -1. This leaves it up to the optimization algorithm to decide from which origin to which destination the lines run. The relationship between the line od list and the line path matrix remains the same as for passenger routing. The path of the line can also be freely selected, taking the infrastructure and the needs of the passengers into account. The only restriction is, that branches are not allowed, which means there is at most one option on how to proceed for each station. As more than one line is usually to be taken into account, several line path matrices are also stored here in the so-called binary line variable L^{bin} . The variable is called *binary* line variable, because the line paths matrices always characterize line paths, but not how often lines are circulating. How frequencies are modelled, is described in chapter 4.13. The maximum of allowed lines is set during parameter selection and is given as k .

Line conservation constraint

$$\sum_{j \in V} L_{l,i,j}^{bin} - \sum_{j \in V} L_{l,i,j}^{bin} = O_{l,i} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \quad (2)$$

- The binary line variable has the value range $L^{bin} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V \times V}$.
- The line od variable has the value range $O \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{K \times V}$.

4.12.1 Line origin-destination variable absolute value constraint

This constraint is to determine the absolute value of the line origin-destination list $|O_{l,i}|$. In the code, the absolute value was implemented with two inequalities. This needs to be made in this way because the optimization algorithm doesn't support direct absolute values as described by Gurobi Optimization 2024.

$$|O_{l,i}| \geq O_{l,i} \quad \forall l \in K, \quad i \in V \quad (3)$$

$$|O_{l,i}| \geq -O_{l,i} \quad \forall l \in K, \quad i \in V \quad (4)$$

- The absolute value of the line od variable O has the value range $|O| \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V}$.

$$|O_{l,i}| \geq \begin{cases} 1, & \forall O_{l,i} = 1 \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \\ 0, & \forall O_{l,i} = 0 \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \\ 1, & \forall O_{l,i} = -1 \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

- As $O_{l,j} = 0$ is not uniquely defined, the use of the two constraints to calculate the absolute value may be problematic in general cases.
- In this specific case, $|O|$ is only used in 7, in which higher values (1 instead of 0) don't lead to advantages.

4.12.2 Line origin-destination variable number constraint

The sum of all nodes for a line origin-destination list O_l has to be zero, since the sum of +1, -1, and any number of 0s is always 0, as well as the sum of any number of 0s when no line is necessary. The sum of all nodes for the absolute values of a line origin-destination list O_l has to be smaller or equal to 2. This is because it is not allowed to have more than one origin and destination, which would result in a result higher than two. The two constraints combined ensure that the definition of the origin and destination works correctly.

$$\sum_{i \in V} O_{l,i} = 0 \quad \forall l \in K \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} |O_{l,i}| \leq 2 \quad \forall l \in K \quad (7)$$

4.12.3 Line branch constraint

Lines must always follow a clear path without interruptions or branches. Therefore the sum of each row has to be smaller or equal to one to avoid branches.

$$\sum_{j \in V} L_{l,i,j}^{bin} \leq 1 \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \quad (8)$$

4.13 Frequency assignment

Frequency assignment is a central pillar in a line planning problem, as it determines the capacity provided by each line. In frequency assignment, a distinction must be made between predefined and therefore unchangeable lines and changeable lines. If the frequency variable is applied to the unchangeable lines, a constant is multiplied by a variable, which results in a linear condition. However, if the frequency per line is multiplied by a line that is also being optimized, this results in a quadratic condition. These can make solving an optimization problem much more difficult (Gurobi Optimization 2024). For this reason, several different variants have been implemented to enable a comparison of the computing time.

4.13.1 Predefined Lines

The predefined lines are discussed first, as there is never a quadratic constraint. If the line paths are given by a line pool, these line paths are stored as binary line matrices in G . The

line frequency Q is multiplied by G , which has the same structure as L^{bin} . The result is stored in the line variable L .

Line frequency assignment constraint

$$G_{l,i,j} \cdot Q_l = L_{l,i,j} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (9)$$

- The predefined line constant has the value range $G \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V \times V}$.
- The line frequency variable has the value range $Q_l \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^K$, where m is the maximum frequency.
- The line variable has the value range $L_{l,i,j} \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{K \times V \times V}$.

4.13.2 Direct multiplication

In the case of variable lines, frequency assignment may be working the same as for predefined lines. Here the binary line path matrix is multiplied by an integer frequency variable. This results in quadratic constraints.

$$L_{l,i,j}^{bin} \cdot Q_l = L_{l,i,j} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (10)$$

4.13.3 Linearization

It is possible to linearize multiplications between a continuous variable and a binary variable (Asghari et al. 2022). As the line path matrix is already available as a binary variable, this method is applied here. These constraints are all linear constraints.

$$L_{l,i,j} \leq L_{l,i,j}^{bin} \cdot m \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (11)$$

$$L_{l,i,j} \leq Q_l \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (12)$$

$$L_{l,i,j} \geq Q_l + m \cdot (L_{l,i,j}^{bin} - 1) \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (13)$$

$$L_{l,i,j} \geq 0 \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (14)$$

4.13.4 Line groups

Often, two lines are provided for each line path, each serving one direction. These two lines may be combined into a line group. All the lines within one line group share the same frequency. Therefore a new constraint is introduced:

$$\sum_{f=1}^m Q_{E_l}^{group} = Q_l \quad \forall l \in K \quad (15)$$

- The line group frequency variable has the value range $Q^{group} \in \mathbb{E} \cap [0, m]^e$.
- The line group assignment list has the value range $E \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, e]^k$

The line group assignment list has one item per line and assigns this item the list to a line group.

4.14 Line and Flow Aggregation

The passenger flow and the lines are stored in individual matrices in F and L . However, to obtain a complete picture of all passenger flows and lines, the passenger flow has to be aggregated as well as the lines. This means that the individual matrices are summed element by element into an aggregated flow variable and an aggregated line variable.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 14: Passenger path 1

Figure 15: Passenger path 2

Figure 16: Aggregated passenger paths

The matrices 14 and 15 show two passenger paths, one runs from 1 via 2 and 3 to 4, and the second from 1 via 2 and 4 to 3. The matrix 16 shows the result of the element-by-element summation. This matrix is called aggregated flow variable F_{agg} for the passenger paths and aggregated line variable L_{agg} for the line paths.

4.14.1 Flow aggregation constraint

The passenger path matrices stored in the flow variable F are summed element-wise. The result is stored in the aggregated flow variable F^{agg} .

$$\sum_{h \in V} F_{h,i,j} = F_{i,j}^{agg} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (16)$$

- The aggregated flow variable has the value range $F^{agg} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$.

4.14.2 Line aggregation constraint

The line path matrices stored in the line variable L are summed element-wise. The result is stored in the aggregated line variable L^{agg} .

$$\sum_{l \in K} L_{l,i,j} = L_{i,j}^{agg} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (17)$$

- The aggregated line variable has the value range $L^{agg} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$.

4.15 Capacity constraints

The two aggregated variables F_{agg} and L_{agg} ensure, that all passengers are transported by a vehicle circulating on a line and that the vehicles don't overcrowd the infrastructure.

4.15.1 Vehicle capacity constraint

The vehicle capacity constraint multiplies the aggregated lines L^{agg} with the vehicle capacity c and links this result to the aggregated flow F^{agg} . The flow of each edge has to be smaller or equal to the line transport capacity.

$$L_{i,j}^{agg} \cdot c \geq F_{i,j}^{agg} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (18)$$

- The vehicle capacity c has a value range $c \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$.

4.15.2 Infrastructure capacity constraint

The infrastructure capacity constraint links the aggregated lines L^{agg} with the infrastructure capacity I . The infrastructure capacity matrix is a matrix indicating the maximum of vehicles circulating between two edges, which has to be met by the actual number of vehicles circulating between two edges.

$$L_{i,j}^{agg} \leq I_{i,j} \quad \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (19)$$

- The infrastructure capacity I has a value range $I \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$.

4.16 Subtour Elimination

The elimination of line subtours is crucial to omit disconnected line paths within one line. Therefore the concept of secondary lines is introduced, considering the already introduced lines, which are called here primary lines to distinguish them from the secondary lines. The secondary lines link the origin of one primary line with all intermediate and the destination node of the primary line. Then it is enforced, that the primary line may only be routed along secondary

line paths. To route the secondary lines, a new variable D has to be introduced, which works similarly to the line origin-destination variable O , but contains an origin-destination list for each secondary line.

4.16.1 Upper and lower bound for the secondary line origin-destination variable

The origin node of the secondary lines has to be determined using the line od variable O . The line od variable contains a list for each primary line, in which the origin is stored as 1 and the destination as -1. If there is a 1 in the list, then the respective position in the secondary line origin-destination list is an origin as well, except if there are fewer intermediate and origin nodes than lists for secondary lines. This is clarified by the following example in 17 and 18 showing a line running from 1 via 2 to 3. As node 4 is not an intermediate or origin node of the primary line, secondary line 4 remains with 0s. The same is true for secondary line 1, which would have the same origin and destination node.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 17: Line od list

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 18: Line path matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 19: Secondary line 1

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 20: Secondary line 2 with destination node 2

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 21: Secondary line 3 with destination node 3

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 22: Secondary line 4

The origin position in the secondary line variable may either be 0 (secondary lines 1 and 4 in vectors 19 and 22) or 1 (secondary lines 2 and 3 in vectors 20 and 21). If there is a 0 or -1 (intermediate, blank, or destination node) in the primary line od list, the respective position in the secondary line origin-destination list is either a destination or blank node (-1 or 0), as we don't get additional information about intermediate nodes out of a 0 or -1 in the line od variable.

The intermediate nodes have to be determined using the line variable L . If there is a 1 in the line path matrix, this is always an intermediate node, which results in a destination node in the associated secondary line od list (secondary lines 2 and 3). If there is a 0 in the line

variable, it is never an intermediate node, but it may be an origin or a blank node, therefore the value in the secondary line origin-destination variable is either 0 or 1. An overview of all cases is provided by table 2.

line origin-destination variable		
given value	upper bound	lower bound
1	1	0
0	0	-1
-1	0	-1

line variable		
given value	upper bound	lower bound
1	-1	-1
0	1	0

Table 2: Upper and lower bound of the secondary line od variable

As the information provided with the upper and lower boundaries doesn't provide sufficient information to route a secondary line with this list, an additional constraint has to be introduced, stating that the sum of each list in the secondary line origin-destination variable has to be 0. As there are some lists with a fixed -1 for the destination node, these lists need one value of 1 to balance the sum. The list position of the origin node is the only position, which may be 1, all other positions are either defined as -1 or as 0. Therefore the origin node is fixed as 1, the destination node as -1, and all other nodes as 0.

The following constraints determine the upper and lower bound.

Lower bound for the origin node

$$O_{l,j} + |O_{l,j}| \cdot 0.5 - 1 \leq D_{l,j,i} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (20)$$

This is the lower bound, which ensures, using the line origin-destination variable O , that the node of an origin has at least a 0 and that all other nodes have at least a -1 in the secondary line origin-destination variable V .

- The secondary line od variable has the value range $D \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{K \times V \times V}$.
- D consists of one list for each primary line, in which are stored n lists for the secondary lines each with a length of n .

Upper bound for the origin node

$$O_{l,j} + |O_{l,j}| \cdot 0.5 \geq D_{l,j,i} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (21)$$

This is the upper bound, which ensures, using the line origin-destination variable $O_{l,j}$, that the node of an origin has at most a +1 and all other nodes have at most a 0 in the secondary line origin-destination variable $V_{l,j,i}$.

Lower bound for the intermediate node

$$-L_{l,i,j}^{bin} \leq D_{l,j,i} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (22)$$

This is the lower bound, which ensures, using the binary line variable $L_{l,i,j}^{bin}$, that the node of the intermediate node has at least a -1 and all the other nodes have at least a 0 in the secondary line origin-destination variable $V_{l,j,i}$.

Upper bound for the intermediate node

$$-2 \cdot L_{l,i,j}^{bin} + 1 \geq D_{l,j,i} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (23)$$

This is the upper bound, which ensures, using the binary line variable $L_{l,i,j}^{bin}$, that the node of the intermediate node has at most a -1 and all the other nodes have at most a 1 in the secondary line origin-destination variable $V_{l,j,i}$.

Line origin-destination variable number constraint

$$\sum_{i \in V} D_{l,j,i} = 0 \quad \forall l \in K, j \in V \quad (24)$$

The sum of all nodes for a secondary line origin-destination list $D_{l,j}$ has to be zero, since the sum of +1, -1, and any number of 0s is always 0, as well as the sum of any number of 0s when no line is necessary.

4.16.2 Different options to solve the subtour elimination problem

There are two ways on how to solve the subtour elimination problem. The straightforward way defines a line path matrix for each subline, meaning that there are up to n sublines per primary line, which is resource-intensive. The other approach is to use only one line path matrix per primary line, in which all secondary lines are routed. This is similar to the approach merging the passenger path matrices in 4.11. This means, that all secondary lines departing from the same node are routed in the same line path matrix. An example may be seen in figures 23 to 25.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 23: Secondary line 2 with destination node 2

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 24: Secondary line 3 with destination node 3

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 25: Summed secondary lines

Secondary line conservation constraint

$$\sum_{j \in V} C_{l,i,j} - \sum_{j \in V} C_{l,j,i} = \sum_{j \in V} D_{l,i,j} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V \quad (25)$$

The right term sums the secondary line od vectors into one merged vector as shown in figure 23. The secondary line conservation constraint ensures, that each set of secondary lines per primary line is routed in one line path matrix along the network.

- The secondary line variable has the value range $C \in \mathbb{Z}^{K \times V \times V}$.

Secondary line to primary line constraint

$$C_{l,i,j} \leq L_{l,i,j}^{bin} \cdot M \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V \quad (26)$$

The secondary line to primary line constraint ensures, that all secondary line paths stored in C_l may only be routed along the primary line L_l^{bin} . This guarantees that the original line must be routed in a way that all intermediate nodes are included in one path. If $L_{l,i,j}^{bin}$ is 0, no path along the respective edge is possible for secondary lines. Contrary if $L_{l,i,j}^{bin}$ is 1, then a large number of secondary paths may be routed along this path.

- The constant M is used for the so-called Big M method, needed for indicator constraints to replace if/else terms (Lubin et al. 2023).
- The M constant has a for this specific case sufficient high value, also called the Big M constant.

4.17 Variables in two-stage modeling

As this model is part of a two-stage optimization, several of the variables and the infrastructure matrix appear in the first and second stage with different values, but a similar structure. In the second stage, the variables and the infrastructure constant may also be different for each scenario. All the second-stage variables get one more dimension, indicated by the index $s \in S$,

which denotes the scenario. The following table 3 gives an overview of the variables and their use in the two stages. The difference variables, the line rerouting determination variable as well as the reduced infrastructure matrix will be introduced in the two following subsections and are only part of the second stage. The composition of the constraints in the two stages is explained in section 4.9.

General variable name	First stage variable	Second stage variable
$F_{h,i,j}$	$F_{h,i,j}^{s1} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V \times V}$	$F_{s,h,i,j}^{s2} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times V \times V \times V}$
$F_{i,j}^{agg}$	$F_{i,j}^{agg,s1} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	$F_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times V \times V}$
$L_{l,i,j}$	$L_{l,i,j}^{s1} \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{K \times V \times V}$	$L_{s,l,i,j}^{s2} \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{S \times K \times V \times V}$
$L_{l,i,j}^{bin}$	$L_{l,i,j}^{bin,s1} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V \times V}$	$L_{s,l,i,j}^{bin,s2} \in \{0, 1\}^{S \times K \times V \times V}$
$L_{i,j}^{agg}$	$L_{i,j}^{agg,s1} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	$L_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times V \times V}$
$O_{l,i}$	$O_{l,i}^{s1} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{K \times V}$	$O_{l,i}^{s1} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{K \times V}$
$ O_{l,i} $	$ O_{l,i}^{s1} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V}$	$ O_{l,i}^{s1} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times V}$
Q_l	$Q_l^{s1} \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^k$	$Q_{s,l}^{s2} \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{S \times k}$
$Q_{l,f}^{bin}$	$Q_{l,f}^{bin,s1} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times m}$	$Q_{s,l,f}^{bin,s2} \in \{0, 1\}^{S \times K \times m}$
$C_{l,i,j}$	$C_{l,i,j}^{s1} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{K \times V \times V}$	$C_{s,l,i,j}^{s2} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times K \times V \times V}$
$D_{l,j,i}$	$D_{l,j,i}^{s1} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{K \times V \times V}$	$D_{s,l,j,i}^{s2} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{S \times K \times V \times V}$
$I_{i,j}$	$I_{i,j}^{s1} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	$I_{s,i,j}^{s2} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times V \times V}$

Table 3: Utilization of variables in the two stages

- The stage of the variables and the constant is denoted by $s1$ and $s2$.
- The set of scenarios is given by S .
- The scenario of the variables and the constant is denoted by the index $s \in S$.

4.18 Difference constraints

To determine differences between the second and first stage in terms of line paths and frequencies, two difference variables are introduced respectively.

4.18.1 Line difference constraints

This constraint determines the difference between the line variable of the second stage L^{s2} and the line variable of the first stage L^{s1} . The difference variable ΔL represents the adaptations resulting from line replanning.

$$\Delta L_{s,l,i,j} = L_{s,l,i,j}^{s2} - L_{l,i,j}^{s1} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (27)$$

- The line difference variable ΔL has a value range $\Delta L \in \mathbb{Z}^{S \times K \times V \times V}$.

The following constraints determine the absolute value of the line difference variable $\Delta L_{l,i,j}$, needed for evaluating replanning costs.

$$|\Delta L_{s,l,i,j}| \geq \Delta L_{s,l,i,j} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (28)$$

$$|\Delta L_{s,l,i,j}| \geq -\Delta L_{s,l,i,j} \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (29)$$

- The absolute line difference variable $|\Delta L|$ has a value range $|\Delta L| \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times K \times V \times V}$.

4.18.2 Frequency difference constraints

This constraint determines the difference between the frequency variable of the second stage Q^{s2} and the frequency variable of the first stage Q^{s1} .

$$\Delta Q_{s,l} = Q_{s,l}^{s2} - Q_l^{s1} \quad \forall l \in K, s \in S \quad (30)$$

- The frequency difference variable ΔQ has a value range $\Delta Q \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [-m, m]^{S \times k}$.

The following constraints determine the absolute value of the frequency difference variable $|\Delta Q|$, needed for evaluating replanning costs.

$$|\Delta Q_{s,l}| \geq \Delta Q_{s,l} \quad \forall l \in K, s \in S \quad (31)$$

$$|\Delta Q_{s,l}| \geq -\Delta Q_{s,l} \quad \forall l \in K, s \in S \quad (32)$$

- The absolute frequency difference variable $|\Delta Q|$ has a value range $|\Delta Q| \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{S \times k}$.

4.18.3 Passenger path difference constraints

This constraint determines the difference between the flow variable of the second stage F^{s2} and the flow variable of the first stage L^{s1} . The difference variable ΔF represents the adaptations resulting from the line replanning.

$$\Delta F_{s,h,i,j} = F_{s,h,i,j}^{s2} - F_{h,i,j}^{s1} \quad \forall h \in V, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (33)$$

- The passenger path difference variable ΔF has a value range $\Delta F \in \mathbb{Z}^{S \times V \times V \times V}$.

The following constraints determine the absolute value of the passenger path difference variable $\Delta L_{l,i,j}$, needed for evaluating replanning costs.

$$|\Delta F_{s,l,i,j}| \geq \Delta F_{s,h,i,j} \quad \forall h \in V, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (34)$$

$$|\Delta F_{s,l,i,j}| \geq -\Delta F_{s,h,i,j} \quad \forall h \in V, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (35)$$

- The absolute passenger path difference variable $|\Delta F|$ has a value range $|\Delta F| \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times V \times V \times V}$.

4.19 Replanning Constraints

Replanning only becomes relevant in the second stage. There, however, it allows the passenger paths and frequencies of all lines to be adjusted and lines that are affected by route closures to be rerouted. Additional costs are incurred for frequency adjustments and detours, which are either added to the objective value or deducted from a replanning budget. The first step is to check whether lines can be rerouted at all. The line rerouting determination constraint is introduced for this purpose.

4.19.1 Line rerouting determination constraint

This constraint evaluates, if a line may be rerouted due to infrastructure constraints in the second stage. To allow rerouting, the infrastructure capacity has to be reduced to 0 in the respective edge. The line rerouting determination variable W is zero, if there is no infrastructure closure on the line and a positive integer for all closed edges affecting the line path. An adapted version is used for the infrastructure matrix $I^{s2,base}$, which contains a 0 for blocked edges and a 1 for uninterrupted edges, regardless of the actual capacity. This makes it possible to evaluate the condition correctly.

$$W_{s,l} = \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (L_{s,l,i,j}^{bin,s2}) - \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (I_s^{s2,base} \cdot L_{s,l,i,j}^{bin,s2}) \quad \forall l \in K, s \in S \quad (36)$$

- The line rerouting determination variable has the value range $W \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{S \times k}$.
- The reduced infrastructure capacity matrix for the second stage has the value range $I^{s2,base} \in \{0, 1\}^{V \times V}$.

4.19.2 Line replanning allowance constraint

If the line rerouting determination variable W is 0, then no difference between the first and second stage line variable $L^{s2,bin}$ resp. $L^{s1,bin}$ is allowed. If the variable W is bigger than 0, then unrestricted differences are allowed for the specific line. The rerouting for individual lines works with the same constraints as described in chapter 4.12.

$$L_{s,l,i,j}^{s2,bin} - L_{l,i,j}^{s1,bin} \leq M \cdot W_l \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (37)$$

$$L_{s,l,i,j}^{s2,bin} - L_{l,i,j}^{s1,bin} \geq -M \cdot W_l \quad \forall l \in K, i \in V, j \in V, s \in S \quad (38)$$

4.19.3 Replanning budget

If there is a replanning budget indicated during parameter setting, the replanning cost of the frequency replanning (first term), the line replanning (second term), and the passenger path

adaptions (third term) must stay below budget b .

$$\sum_{l \in K} (d \cdot |\Delta Q_{s,l}|) + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} \sum_{l \in K} (e \cdot |\Delta L_{s,l,i,j}|) + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} \sum_{h \in V} (o \cdot |\Delta F_{s,h,i,j}|) \leq b \quad s \in S \quad (39)$$

- The frequency replanning costs d have a value range $f \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.
- The line replanning costs e have a value range $e \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.
- The passenger path replanning costs o have a value range $o \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.
- The replanning budget b has a value range $b \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.

4.20 Objective Value

The objective value takes into account the optimization result of the first stage and the optimization result of the second stage, both weighted the same. The objective value always considers travel costs from passengers as well as line costs from the operator. Furthermore, replanning costs are added in the second stage, if there is no replanning budget given.

4.20.1 Objective value function without replanning costs

The objective function is composed of the travel time $T_{i,j}$ times the aggregated passenger flow F^{agg} and the line operation cost of the operator R times the aggregated line variable L^{agg} . The parameter w represents the weight of the line operation cost. This objective value function is applied to the first as well as the second stage.

$$\min \left(\sum_{s \in S} \left(\left(\sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (T_{i,j} \cdot F_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2}) \cdot (1-w) + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (R_{i,j} \cdot L_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2}) \cdot w \right) \cdot \xi_s \right) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (T_{i,j} \cdot F_{i,j}^{agg,s1}) \cdot (1-w) + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} (R_{i,j} \cdot L_{i,j}^{agg,s1}) \cdot w \right) \quad (40)$$

- The travel cost matrix T has a value range $T \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$.
- The line cost matrix R has a value range $R \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$.
- The weight of line operating cost w has a value range $w \in [0, 1]$.

4.20.2 Objective value function with replanning costs

The difference to the objective value function without replanning are the terms for frequency replanning, line replanning, and passenger path replanning. The terms for travel time costs and line operating costs are in the first row for the second stage and in the third row for the first stage respectively. The terms for the replanning cost are in the second row. d , e , and o

represent the replanning costs of the frequency, the line and passenger paths. The frequency replanning term adds a penalty for changes in frequency. Each change in the frequency, either up or down, counts to the penalty. The length of the line is not relevant for the calculation of the frequency replanning penalty. The line replanning adds a penalty for changes in the routing of a line. Each edge, which is not served anymore, counts once and every edge, which is served newly, is counted as well once. The frequency of the line is not relevant for the calculation of the line replanning penalty. The passenger path adaptations count the individual changes in the passenger flow matrices.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min \left(\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left(\left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} (T_{i,j} \cdot F_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2}) \cdot (1-w) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} (R_{i,j} \cdot L_{s,i,j}^{agg,s2}) \cdot w \right. \right. \right. \\
& + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{K}} (d \cdot |\Delta Q_{s,l}|) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{K}} (e \cdot |\Delta L_{s,l,i,j}|) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{h \in \mathcal{V}} (o \cdot |\Delta F_{s,h,i,j}|) \left. \left. \right) \cdot \xi_s \right) \quad (41) \\
& \left. + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} (T_{i,j} \cdot F_{i,j}^{agg,s1}) \cdot (1-w) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}} (R_{i,j} \cdot L_{i,j}^{agg,s1}) \cdot w \right)
\end{aligned}$$

5 Results

Various test series were executed with all kinds of parameter combinations, infrastructure restrictions, and procedures. The most important parameters and settings are given at the beginning of each test series. All series were executed with the same line pool (except the replanning cost series), but not always the same number of lines is used. Almost all series are made using the standard scenarios. The standard scenarios and the line pool are given in plot 3 and 4. Scenario 1 (dashed lines) has a probability of 40% and scenario 2 (dotted lines) has a probability of 60%. The objective value is composed of the travel time cost and line operation cost of the first stage and with the same weight as the travel time cost and line operation cost of the second stage. Additionally replanning costs are added to the objective value. This means, that the first stage, the undisturbed line plan is weighted slightly below 50% of the total costs and the second stage a little bit above 50%, depending on the value of the replanning costs. In return, there is no undisturbed scenario in the second stage. This accounts for the two-stage replanning approach, where the first stage line plan is used for all undisturbed cases, whereas if there are restrictions, the line plans of the second stage are used. It would be also possible to introduce an undisturbed second-stage scenario, which has a similar function compared to the first-stage undisturbed line plan and in return, the cost of the first-stage line plan would be omitted in the objective value function. All series are produced using the first approach, however, there is a comparison between the two approaches in subsection 5.7.

5.1 Weighted Travel and Line Cost

Line operation costs and travel time costs are two ways to measure the quality of a line plan. One option would be to optimize only the travel time costs and to give a budget for the line operating costs as proposed by Schöbel 2012. The problem with this approach is the difficulty of assessing a good value for a budget constraint, especially when comparing a lot of different combinations of parameters. Therefore the line operating costs and the travel time costs are both part of the objective value. An additional problem of using budgets was discovered in the replanning budget subsection 5.3. Using too loose cost budgets leads to very long calculation times and should therefore be omitted. As the costs don't reflect reality, the height of the costs was set so that the travel time costs and line operating costs are roughly in the same range. It is possible to weigh the two cost blocks to assess the behavior for different priorities (travel time costs are valued higher vs. line operating costs are valued higher). To assess the impact of different weights, a test series was started. This test series includes one set of runs with the integral procedure and one set with the separated procedure.

The optimization runs are made with the following parameters:

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	1%
Network nodes	18	Number of lines	22
Weight of line costs	0% - 100% in steps of 5%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	100	Cost of line replanning	500

Table 4: Optimization parameters for different weights

Figure 26: Weighted travel and line cost, cost plot 1

The first thing to note in plot 26 are the two series of the objective value. As expected, the integral set of runs performs always better than the separated runs. This is because the first stage line plan anticipates restrictions in the second stage and therefore adapts the lines to reduce replanning costs. The second thing to note is the travel costs. As expected the travel costs rise with a higher weight of the line costs. There doesn't seem to be consistency if the integral or separated set of runs performs better for travel cost or line cost. However, the big drop in the line costs from a line weight of 55% to 60% is visible. In the first stage, the light blue line running east-west is canceled and the frequency of the green line running north-south is reduced by one. In exchange, the frequency of the east-west running violet line is increased

by one. With these adaptations, the lines cost fall significantly, whereas the travel costs increase. Additional implications are visible in plot 27. Replanning costs almost double for the same step. This is due to a worse first-stage line plan to fit the needs of the second-stage line plan.

Figure 27: Weighted travel and line cost, cost plot 2

Generally speaking, total line replanning costs are higher compared with total frequency replanning costs. On one hand, this is due to the much higher costs (500 vs. 100) of line replanning. On the other side, line replanning could be omitted if lines were reduced to a frequency of zero. There seems to be an advantage to using line replanning nevertheless this is more expensive. Not striking are the higher frequency replanning costs for the separated optimization runs, as more replanning is necessary, if no adaption is possible.

5.2 Number of lines

The bigger the line pool is, the more likely good lines are available. The influence of this effect should be investigated with this test series. The optimization runs are made with the following parameters:

5.2.1 General Overview

Parameter	Value		
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	1%
Network nodes	7 - 24	Number of lines	10 - 22 in steps of 2
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	100	Cost of line replanning	500

Table 5: Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets

Figure 28: Costs of different line numbers

Before going into details, plot 28 shows the relation between all different numbers of nodes, the number of lines, and the respective objective value. The first guess seems to be confirmed. The objective value is falling for all network sizes. Some are falling faster as the network with a size of 11 nodes, others slower as for the network with 12 nodes. This is highly dependent on specific lines and networks.

5.2.2 Network with 18 Nodes

The test series for the plots 29 and 30 were made using a network with 18 nodes, all other parameters remain the same.

Figure 29: Costs of different line numbers

The falling object value for a higher number of lines in the line pool is confirmed in the more detailed plot. There is a big step when adding the 15. and 16. line. This new red line for the first second-stage scenario adds new paths for travelers, but it allows also for better usage of the lines and thus a reduction in the total number of offered services, which is visible in the drop in line costs. At the same time, the light blue line in the first-stage line plan is canceled. Adding additional lines leads to further capacity optimizations. This is reversed with the last new, orange line. This line adds additional operating costs but reduces travel costs. This wouldn't be sufficient alone to get to a lower objective value, but the replanning costs have to be included in the analysis as well, which are visible in the next plot.

Figure 30: Costs of different line numbers

The replanning cost plot shows, that the line replanning costs drop significantly with the addition of the orange line (lines 21 and 22), which mainly explains why this result is preferable, even though the line operation costs are higher. The other major drop falls together with the addition of the red line, which is not affected by line closures and thus offers alternative ways to further provide the necessary services. The frequency replanning costs rise with additional lines, which is in line with a change in the replanning strategy. The more alternative, unrestricted lines are available, the less line replannings are necessary, but the more frequency adaptations have to be made to provide line plans without over or under capacity in the first and second stage. The comparison between the integral and separated runs doesn't show anomalies. The objective value is always slightly higher for separated runs and all other data series don't show a consistent behavior except the frequency replanning series. Here it is visible, that the separated procedure is always above the integrated procedure, taking into account the need for additional frequency replanning.

5.3 Replanning Budget

Replanning costs are a central aspect of the adaptations, which are necessary due to the infrastructure restrictions. Therefore it is interesting to assess the influence of different replanning budgets for the objective value. The lower the allowed replanning budget is, the less flexibility is possible to make adjustments between the first and second stage. Thus the first stage has to be better adapted to the individual scenarios of the second stage.

The optimization runs are made with the following parameters and line pool:

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	1%
Network nodes	18	Number of lines	14
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	0 - 10 ⁴ in steps of 100
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	100	Cost of line replanning	500

Table 6: Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets

Figure 31: Line plan with 18 nodes and 14 lines

The infrastructure with 18 nodes and a line pool with 14 lines is considerably reduced in complexity and provides fewer redundancies to serve nodes, as shown in plot 31.

Figure 32: Replanning budget, cost plot 1

The first cost plot 32 shows, that the total costs are falling the higher the replanning budget is. Higher replanning budgets allow for bigger differences between the first and second stage and thus better adaptations for the individual needs of the stages. Comparing the integral and the separated optimization series, integral optimization is in most of the cases equal, sometimes slightly better, and in a few cases worse concerning the objective value. Why is it not always better? This has to do with the optimization gap. Sometimes, especially for a higher replanning budget, it takes a long time to find the best solution. The separated procedure is generally much faster compared with the integrated procedure. Therefore it is much more probable, that the separated procedure finds the optimal solution within time, whereas the integrated procedure fails to find the best solution within 60 minutes. In this case, the separated procedure is indeed better for finding good solutions quickly. Remarkable is, that the first solvable model for separated optimization starts with a replanning budget of 4300 whereas the integral model starts with 4000. While the line replanning costs remain at 4000 the same for both procedures, the frequency replanning costs have to be at least 201 (one more than the previous step of 4200) for the separated procedure. This is due to necessary adaptations for the second state line plans. For scenario 1 this means that the model needed to replace the omitted light blue line (having a frequency of 1 in the first stage) with the orange line (frequency increases from 2 to 3). Additionally, the dark green line is introduced. This costs 240 ($3 * 2 * 100 * 40\%$) for scenario 1 and 0 for scenario 2, as no frequency replanning was necessary. At the very beginning of the integrated series, an increase of 100 in terms of replanning budget may lower the travel time cost by almost 2000, which seems to be a very good trade-off. This later turns into the opposite. The travel time costs show, that no big difference between integrated and

separated runs is visible. After the first initial drop, further improvement of the travel costs are much more expensive in terms of replanning cost. However, for the line operation costs, a much longer fall until the line operation cost stabilize may be seen. It seems that the line operation costs are benefiting more from a bigger replanning budget.

One major problem with the chosen network is, that for roughly 80% of all tests, the first-stage line plans are equal, especially also between the two procedures. Therefore the differences between the two series are often nonexistent.

Figure 33: Replanning budget, cost plot 2

In the replanning cost plot 33, hardly any difference between the integrated and separated procedure is visible. The frequency replanning costs seem to stagnate starting with a replanning budget of 8'000. Everything necessary in terms of frequency is adapted to optimality to this point. However, the line replanning costs always use the whole remaining replanning budget. But the objective value doesn't seem to get a lot of advantages of this excessive replanning. For the replanning budget of 12'500 for the integrated run, the violet line has a length of 15 edges, compared to the original three edges. The problem with high replanning budgets is not only the almost unavailable advantage for the objective value but also the excessive computational running time, which is up to 10 times longer than the most restrictive possible budget or an integration into the objective value function.

5.4 Replanning costs

Different heights of replanning costs affect the similarity between the first-stage and second-stage line plans. Free replanning would mean, that the objective value function doesn't value any similarity and therefore each line plan is optimal for itself. The higher the replanning costs are, the more similar the line plans are. The optimization runs are made with the following parameters and line pool:

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	1%
Network nodes	18	Number of lines	14
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	100	Cost of line replanning	500

Table 7: Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets

Figure 34: Line plan, 14 nodes, 18 lines

This network in plot 34 is slightly different than the previous one, not only in terms of the smaller size but also with a new line path for the brown-orange line going to node 16 instead of 10, adding an unrestricted connection to node 16.

Figure 35: Replanning cost, cost plot 1

The first thing visible in plot 35 is the skyrocketing objective value for the separated approach, whereas the integrated objective value is only a bit higher. Why is that? If the first and second stage is separated, the first stage is not able to adapt to the restrictions in the second stage, thus the line plan is only optimal for the first stage. The second stage line plans however need expensive replanning measures to deal with the restrictions. The integrated procedure may adapt the first-stage line plan to better fit the second-stage line plans. The higher travel cost and line cost for the integrated procedure can be explained by the high costs to provide a shared line plan for both stages and all scenarios. In this line plan, only lines are allowed, which are not affected by both restrictions, which restrict the number of usable lines, which hurts especially in the first stage. If the line plan is shared by all stages and scenarios, this is a strictly robust line plan. The travel costs for high replanning costs in the separated procedure are only 2% higher compared to low replanning costs. The line operation costs are 16% higher, but that comes at a high price of skyrocketing total replanning costs. The line plan of the integrated tests with the highest replanning costs are equal for all stages and scenarios, resulting in a strictly robust line plan. Comparing the costs of this line plan with the best fitting line plans, which are the line plans without replanning costs, 58% higher total costs have to be expected. This is the main disadvantage of strict robustness.

Figure 36: Replanning cost, cost plot 2

The problem with the separated procedure is visible here. While the integrated replanning costs remain low and rise only for medium replanning costs in the in the thousands range, the total replanning costs for the separated procedure are getting very high, even if only the absolute minimum is replanned. What can be seen in plot 36 is, that both replanning strategies can solve the replanning problem alone. This is visible in the last two tests, where only the lower-cost replanning strategy is applied. Interestingly the line cost is 30% lower if only line replanning is applied compared to if only frequency replanning is applied. If the cost of both replanning strategies have the same value, frequency replanning is applied much more often, but line replanning is also used for two cases, proving that a combination often leads to the best results.

Figure 37: Replanning cost, replanning plot

A new plot 37 is introduced here, which shows the weighted average of replannings per each strategy. The weight is the probability of each scenario happening and is in this case 40% for the first scenario (closure of the center east-west edge) and 60% for the second scenario (closure of the north-south edge on the east side). The line replannings are falling for higher line replanning costs, which results in higher line operation costs. The travel costs are less affected. The frequency replannings are starting on a lower level and are only once higher for the integrated procedure compared with the line replannings, for a line replanning cost of 500 and a frequency replanning cost of 100. While for lower replanning costs, the integrated and separate replannings are almost identical, for higher replanning costs the integrated replannings are falling to zero, understandably, and the separated replannings remain on the absolute minimum.

5.5 Different restrictions

Until now, only two scenarios within different parameter settings were tested. Now different scenarios within all parts of the network are tested and compared with each other. Therefore three test sets were set up, each with two scenarios.

5.5.1 Standard Scenarios

The first set is the standard set, used for all tests described above and depicted in figure 3. In scenario one, the edge 10 - 11 on the important east-west route is blocked. This affects three lines, which have important functions in connecting the west and the east parts of the network. The second scenario has a route closure on the eastern north-south route on edge 8 - 16. This blocks the pink, brown, and yellow line. Especially the yellow and brown lines are important to connect the northern part to the southern part of the network. In both sets, three lines may be replanned, which results in a rather big flexibility.

5.5.2 Peripheral Restricted Scenarios

The second set is the peripheral set, which is first introduced here in plot 38.

Figure 38: Line plan with peripheral restrictions

For this set, rather peripheral edges with lower demand and a small number of lines were chosen for closures. This has several implications for the optimization runs. The first is, that fewer passengers are affected due to line closures. The second is, that fewer lines are affected as well, which results in lower replanning procedures, as only a few lines may and have to be replanned. For scenario 1, the edge 12 - 13 with the grey line is affected as well as the edge 20 - 21 with the light blue line. For scenario 2, the edges 4 - 5 with the orange line and the edges 22 - 23 with the green line are affected by the restrictions. Scenario 1 has a probability of 40% and scenario 2 has a probability of 60%.

5.5.3 Heavy Restricted Scenarios

Figure 39: Line plan with heavy restrictions

The third set shown in plot 39 contains heavier and more central restrictions. These restrictions affect a lot of passengers and more than 50% of the lines. This set results in a lot of replanning, especially in line replanning, as in scenario 2 nodes 5 and 6 are only reachable, if line replanning

indeed happened. Concretely in scenario 1, the edges 12 - 11 - 10 - 16 are closed, affecting the dark green, violet, blue, and pink lines. The second restriction on the edges 10 - 9 - 8 - 16 affects the red, blue, orange, pink, yellow, and brown lines. One important caveat concerns the edge 9 - 10. If this edge were fully closed, node 9 couldn't be served by any line. Remember that no branches are allowed, the red and orange lines are not able to serve node 9, even after a path replanning. Therefore edges 9 - 10 remain open with a capacity constraint of 2. However, this concerns the red line, as no line replanning for the red line is allowed anymore. Scenario 1 has a probability of 40% and scenario 2 has a probability of 60%.

5.5.4 Combined Scenarios

To make the ultimate test for the model and the optimization algorithm, all scenarios are combined into one run. This means, that the optimization algorithm has to find a line plan for the first stage and six line plans for the second stage. The probabilities are as follows:

Set	Scenario	Probability
Standard	1	14%
Standard	2	6%
Peripheral	1	10%
Peripheral	2	8%
Restricted	1	5%
Restricted	2	7%
No restrictions		50%

Table 8: Scenario probabilities

5.5.5 Optimization parameters

The optimization runs are made with the following parameters:

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	All from above
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	2%
Network nodes	24	Number of lines	18
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	middle: 200 high: 1000	Cost of line replanning	middle: 1000 high: 5000

Table 9: Optimization parameters for different frequencies and vehicle capacities

Figure 40: Various restrictions, cost plot 1

Starting with the standard scenario in plot 40 both procedures are almost equal in terms of costs, for both high and middle replanning costs. Comparing it with the peripheral set, the two procedures diverge more for the peripheral set and the objective values are similar. However, both the travel time costs and line operation costs are considerably lower, which means that fewer passengers are affected by deviations and fewer lines, and a lower frequency is needed to serve all passengers. The comparison of the first-stage line plans is interesting. Whereas the two line plans of the standard scenario as well as the separated procedure line plan of the peripheral scenario are equal, the integrated line plan of the peripheral scenario is different in terms of line choice and frequency, which is very interesting. For example, the orange line is already omitted in the first stage integrated procedure. Using this approach, no frequency replanning cost at all is necessary, resulting in a lower total cost, even if the line costs are higher. The next test to discuss is the heavy restricted set. First visible is the very high spike for the objective value, which is 24% higher compared with the standard test, while the travel costs are less than 5% higher. The line costs are diverging for the two procedures and are higher for the integrated one and lower for the separated procedure. Very interesting is the combined test, where all scenarios are combined and an unrestricted scenario with a 50% probability is added. The total cost is much lower, compared with all other tests with high replanning costs. This is mainly because of the high probability for the unrestricted scenario, which is very cheap compared to the restricted scenarios. Moreover, the first-stage line plan and the second-stage

line plan for the unrestricted scenario are equal. This shows, that if a considerable part of the scenario probabilities consists of unrestricted scenarios, the incentives to adapt the first-stage line plan to fit the restricted scenarios are often too low. If the first-stage line plan is equal to the unrestricted line plan of the second stage, it is also very probable, that the integrated and separated procedures are equal. For the middle replanning costs, the findings are similar, with generally lower total and line costs, whereas the travel costs remain similar.

Figure 41: Various restrictions, cost plot 2

The replanning cost plot 41 shows the very high line replanning cost for the heavily restricted scenarios. The line replanning cost always exceeds the frequency replanning cost. The deviations between the two procedures are small, with some exceptions, notably the higher line replanning costs for the heavily restricted scenario with high replanning costs. Very interesting are the lower frequency replanning costs for the heavily restricted scenarios and middle replanning costs.

Figure 42: Various restrictions, replanning plot

The replanning plot 42 shows, that there is always a bit more replanning for lower replanning cost, however, this is not the case for the combined scenario. Here the frequency replannings are almost halved compared with the high replanning cost, whereas the line replannings are 50% higher. It seems here, that doing a bit more line replanning is beneficial combined with doing less frequency replanning. Most probable the lower line replanning cost allowed to do a bit more line replanning while reducing the needed frequency replanning. Also interesting is, that for the heavily restricted scenarios almost the same amount of replanning is made, independently of the higher or lower costs.

5.6 Equal Network Capacity, Various Frequencies

Generally, a vehicle capacity of 100 passengers and a maximum frequency of five is set. This allows for diverse frequency values, doesn't restrict many solutions, and protects the computational resources by limiting the number of choices. To see the effect of changing the number of services provided while maintaining the overall capacity constant, two test series were executed.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	0.1%
Network nodes	18	Number of lines	16
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	500 - 38	Maximum frequency	1 - 13
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 10: Optimization parameters for different frequencies and vehicle capacities

Figure 43: Frequency and capacity, cost and utilization plot 1

The plot 43 doesn't show the line operation costs and the objective value, as a comparison between different frequencies for these two values is not very informative. However, the utilization was added, giving an insight into how well the line capacity fits the demand of passengers. Both series are performing as expected with the utilization taking a big step from a maximum frequency of 1 to a maximum frequency of two. The following steps remain smaller but are still going up to 56% utilization. There don't seem significant differences between separated and integrated solving. The travel cost is going down for both procedures. This may be expected as well. While the line costs are not visible here, they nevertheless are part of the objective value. The lower the maximum frequency is, the fewer lines are used to provide a minimum viable

service. Therefore less shortcuts are provided. The better the lines may be fitted to the actual need, the lower the travel costs. The integrated and separated series don't show systematic differences.

Figure 44: Frequency and capacity, cost plot 2

The plot 44 reveals a step from a maximum frequency of 5 to 6. In this step, the violet line started to be replanned in the second stage, before it was just reduced to zero for the first scenario in the second stage. This also allows a higher frequency in the first stage thus allowing more passengers for a path without detours. The only small difference between the two procedures is the maximum frequency of nine. There the south-bound yellow line is rerouted via 8,9,10,16,17 in the integrated procedure. In the separated procedure, node 16 is omitted and the line goes directly from 10 to 17. The frequency replanning series shows the typical behavior for the integrated and separated procedures, the growth for a higher maximum frequency may be explained by the higher frequencies to transport the same amount of passengers and therefore the need to change the frequencies more compared with lower frequencies.

5.7 First Stage or Second Stage Undisturbed Scenario

Line operators may either use the first-stage line plan or a second-stage line plan using an undisturbed scenario as a base for their operations. These tests examine the difference between both approaches. If the undisturbed line plan of the first stage is used, the costs of this line plan

are included in the objective value, otherwise, they are excluded. The probability distributions are equal to the other series, with the only exception if the second stage scenario is used for the undisturbed line plan, this scenario has a probability of 50% and the other two 20% and 30% respectively.

The tests for various network sizes don't show - as expected - any difference for all costs and line plans. Therefore no adaptations are made to the other test series.

5.8 Various Probabilities of the Undisturbed Second-Stage Scenario

To determine for which probability the first-stage line plan and the second-stage line plan for the undisturbed scenario are equal, a test series using only the integrated procedure was carried out. Each test was carried out with a higher probability of an undisturbed scenario coming into effect in the second stage.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated	Optimization gap	0%
Network nodes	14	Number of lines	18
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 11: Optimization parameters for various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario

Figure 45: Various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario, cost plot 1

Plot 45 shows the three scenarios in the second stage (scenario 1 is the undisturbed one). The higher the probability of the undisturbed scenario, the lower the total cost of the undisturbed scenario. However, the total cost of the two disturbed scenarios is growing. One major change is from a probability of 50% to 55% of the undisturbed scenario. The probability of 0% and 100% is not shown, as there is no bound for the cost of the undisturbed respectively the disturbed scenarios.

Figure 46: Various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario, cost plot 2

The replanning cost plot 46 shows, that there is no difference between the first-stage line plan and second-stage undisturbed line plan, except for the first three tests (1%, 3%, and 5%). This is interesting, as it could have been assumed, that this could hold also for higher probabilities. On the other hand, the line replanning cost of scenario 2 rises at the same time. With the probability change from 50% to 55% more line replanning cost is added and scenario 3 has to be replanned as well. The first stage line plan changes here the the dark green line to the pink line. Interestingly, for this parameter set, frequency replannings are much more important than line replannings, indicating that a large line pools with more redundancy enable to use mainly frequency replanning.

5.9 Passenger Path Replanning Costs

Passenger path replannings are as a rule free, which was determined when this thesis started. However, over time, the question arose what would happen if passenger path adaptations were not free. Therefore the code was adapted and this test series was carried out. One first remark to the calculation time. No general rule is visible in contrast to line path and frequency

replanning cost, where the calculation time is longer for lower values. The calculation times for various passenger path adaptations seem to be a bit smaller for lower values, but this finding isn't consistent over all tests. The difference between free passenger path replannings and the other tests with passenger path replanning costs is also not consistent.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated	Optimization gap	0% - 6%
Network nodes	16, 20	Number of lines	18, 22
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 12: Optimization parameters for various probabilities of the undisturbed second-stage scenario

Figure 47: Passenger path replanning costs, cost plot 1

The next two plots (47 and 48) have a logarithmic y-axis to reveal the differences for the lower values. The higher the passenger path replanning cost, the higher the objective value, which may be explained in parts by the total passenger path replanning costs included in the objective value function. But the line operation cost as well as the travel time cost are rising as well. It seems that the high passenger path replanning costs and the second-stage scenarios force passengers to do detours in the first stage only that they don't have to find a new path in the second stage.

Figure 48: Passenger path replanning costs, replannings plot

The replannings plot shows, that the number of passenger path replannings is falling for higher replanning costs, as expected. But there seems to be a pretty consistent minimum of passenger path replannings, which is necessary, independently of the costs associated. The frequency of replannings is doubling with higher passenger path replanning costs, the line replannings are also increasing. It seems that the higher passenger path replanning costs are forcing other replannings to happen more often, which is not intuitive at first. But as both network sizes don't allow for strict robust line plans, for which no replanning at all would be necessary, doing more replanning to provide the passenger with as many good choices as possible is the better strategy.

5.10 Line Optimization

In the methods chapter 4.6, the line optimization setting was mentioned. No line pool is provided, instead a maximum number of lines is given and the optimization algorithm is free to choose the origin and destination, the length and path of the lines. This opens a bunch of new possibilities, which are probably very hard to solve. Therefore a series of tests to compare the line planning option with the line pool option was conducted. The results are very clear: The line planning option works only for seven and eight nodes, and the optimization process for the nine nodes got stuck with a gap of 6%. The duration of the optimization process for 7 and eight nodes was 810 seconds and 930 seconds respectively. The line pool option took less than two seconds for the same network sizes. But, here the line optimization algorithm has clear advantages, the objective value is much lower. If the full line pool is available for the line pool option, then the line optimization approach has up to 17% better results, even though fewer

lines are needed to reach the better result. However, the very poor calculation times don't allow any bigger networks and thus this option isn't able to play a bigger role in this thesis. Nonetheless, parts of the line optimization constraints are needed for line replanning.

5.11 Computational performance

The computational performance of solving two-stage LPP is highly dependent on parameter selection. The most important parameter that determines the variable number is the number of nodes in the network and the number of lines in the line pool. To determine the relation of the number of lines and number of nodes for the computational performance, a series of tests was executed. As the second research question asks about performance differences between integrated and separated two-stage optimization, two series were set up to determine differences in the objective value and computational performance. All tests run independently of each other on six cores with 12 GB to 24 GB of memory, depending on the number of nodes. Without higher memory available, the optimization runs for big networks aborted. No time limit is used for all tests comparing computational performances.

The optimization runs are made with the following parameters:

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	Integrated and separated	Optimization gap	2%
Network nodes	7 - 24	Number of lines	6 - 28
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 13: Optimization parameters for different replanning budgets

Figure 49: Computational performance for different sets of nodes and lines

The scale of the color bar in plot 49 is logarithmic to fit all possible values and to make small differences better visible. Apparent are the big differences from a calculation period of 10 seconds for small networks up to 20'000 seconds or six hours for the biggest network with the highest number of lines. The assumption, that the computational performance is mainly dependent on the number of nodes, is confirmed. The same is valid for the number of lines, whereas it is a little bit less apparent than for the number of nodes. The integrated vs. separated runs show also substantial differences. Doing a regression analysis, shows, that all three independent variables are highly significant (p-value smaller than 10^{-6}) with a higher significance for the number of nodes and the procedure (p-value smaller than 10^{-13}).

All these runs are ideal for comparing the objective value and computational performance difference between the integrated and separated procedure, given in the following table.

Cost comparison	Value
Total costs	1.9%
Travel costs	2.2%
Line costs	2.3%
Frequency replanning costs	-22%
Line replanning costs	1.6%
Calculation time	5.28

Table 14: Cost and calculation time difference between the integrated and separated procedure (the total costs for the separated procedure are higher)

One last word to the 22-node tests: These seem to be incorrect, as results are missing. However, the infrastructure in combination with the line pool has some advantageous and some disadvantageous combinations. Specifically, if 22 nodes are used, demand is added, for which only enough capacity is available, if the red line is added. As soon as node 24 is added, enough capacity is available on the light blue and dark blue lines to transport the additional demand. This example shows as well, that the found results are highly dependent on the network, the line pool, and the parameters. If a higher train capacity or a higher maximum frequency were chosen, the problem for 22 nodes would have been solved with much fewer lines.

5.12 Solving Performance

The process of solving an optimization problem consists of several steps (Gurobi Optimization 2024). The first one is the model-building step. This step is highly dependent on the chosen solver, the simple implementations generally take much shorter compared to the implementation with Stochastic Programs. The memory requirement of Stochastic Programs during this process is immense, as up to 55 GB are used for a 24-node problem with a lot of lines. The long duration of the model-building process with Stochastic Programs is the main reason for the poor performance of all the solving techniques associated with Stochastic Programs.

The second step is the presolving phase. In this phase, the problem is transformed into a smaller and easier solvable state. The problem size may be halved during this process. As the presolving process generally doesn't take more than several minutes, the most aggressive presolving algorithm was chosen for Gurobi.

Figure 50: Gurobi solving process

The third and fourth step is the optimization phase itself. This phase is shown in plot 50. It is separated into two steps, as in-depth analysis showed, that the algorithm first tries to find mainly a first solution and to optimize this solution. Normally this process takes up to 40% of the time for long-running optimization problems. In the second step, the optimum value hardly changes at all. However, the solver tries to tighten the difference between the lower bound and the optimal value. Usually, this takes more than half of the optimization time. Therefore, higher gaps and time limits are used if long optimization runs are anticipated. The choice of good values is hard, in order not to abort too early and to produce unusable results.

5.13 Performance of Various Procedures, Solvers and Settings

During the programming phase, it became evident, that big calculation time differences exist for different solvers, procedures, and settings. However, keeping track of these differences was difficult as so many parameters influence the performance and they are not always linear or logical. Therefore a comprehensive series of tests was conducted to determine objective differences.

5.13.1 Relative Speed of Various Procedures and Solvers

The first test compares the calculation time of the five procedures and solvers with the following parameters and settings.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	Yes
Procedure	All	Optimization gap	0.1%
Network nodes	8 - 20	Number of lines	16, 20
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 15: Relative computational effort of various procedures and solvers

Figure 51: Relative computational effort of procedures and solvers

The plot 51 shows the calculation time differences for various procedures and solvers. Here, the solvers among each other are compared, using the standard setting for all tests. Four-

teen different parameter sets were tested for all solvers and procedures and then the average calculation time was taken to compare the results.

The comparison reveals considerable performance differences. The separated procedures are 40% to 50% faster than the integrated simple solver. This seems to contradict the findings from the tests above, however small parameter changes and different CPU configurations and server performance may have a tremendous influence on the calculation time. Reaching reproducibility is difficult. If the second-stage scenarios are solved independently, the calculation time however is 20% longer compared to a second-stage integral approach. The use of the Stochastic Programs library however proves to not provide sufficient advantages over a simple implementation, as both algorithms (simple solver and progressive hedging) take considerably more time. Especially progressive hedging with a ten times longer calculation time doesn't seem to be a good solution to solve a two-stage LPP. But the problem is not only on the quantitative side, there is also a qualitative problem. The objective values of the separated procedures are on average 0.3% worse than the integrated procedure. This is as expected, but the solvers from Stochastic Programs tend to have similar problems. The simple solver algorithm of Stochastic Programs is on average 0.05% worse than the objective values of the integrated, simple solver. This lies within the gap of 0.1% and if individual tests are repeated with a gap of 0, the problem disappears. The progressive hedging solver however is on average 0.18% worse than the objective value of the integrated, simple solver. This lies outside of the gap of 0.1%. Repeating the tests for networks of size 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 with a gap of 0% show similar problems with a deviation of 0.3% on average. The problem isn't consistent over all tests, two out of six tests show equal results.

Unfortunately, the l-shaped method implemented by Biel et al. 2022 including feasibility cuts and solved with the HiGHS solver provided by Huangfu et al. 2018 was not able to solve the problem. A gap of over 75% persisted over the whole optimization period, which lasted for dozens of minutes for a seven-node network, which should be solvable within seconds. The HiGHS solver managed to solve the same problem without the l-shaped method in under a minute, which is good, but still worse than the Gurobi solver. Using the GLPK solver provided by Oki 2012, independently if it is used as a simple solver or within the l-shaped method, it warns against an ill-conditioned basis matrix. Furthermore, memory leaks often happen, which is not the case for Gurobi and HiGHS. Therefore no further tests were executed with GLPK.

5.13.2 Iterative solving heuristic

All advanced solvers need extensive calculation time (> 120 min) and a lot of memory (> 50 GB) to build models with 24 nodes. All simple solving techniques in contrast need a long time to find a first solution and to converge, but are generally less resource-intensive. For some parameter combinations, the solvers even fail to converge. In contrast, the separation of the first and second-stage heuristics showed very good results. A progressive hedging-like technique was then applied to allow adaptations to the first stage line plan after the second stage

was determined. The objective function of the first stage is adapted to include the differences between the second and first-stage lines and frequencies. This forces the first stage to adapt to the requirements of the second stage. Then the second stage is solved again, considering as well the differences between the first and second stage in the objective function. This is repeated until the differences between the two stages don't change any more.

The results showed no consistent behavior. For most of the parameter sets tested, the objective value lies between the integrated and separated procedures. However, for some sets, the objective value is slightly worse compared with the separated procedure. The calculation speed lies in between the integrated and separated procedure for medium and big networks. As the objective value doesn't show consistent behavior, this algorithm isn't used for the other test series.

5.13.3 Relative Speed of Various Settings

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Network	SiouxFalls	Infra. restrictions	Standard
Optimize lines	No	Eliminate subtours	All
Procedure	All	Optimization gap	0.1%
Network nodes	14, 14, 18, 20	Number of lines	16, 20, 16, 16
Weight of line costs	50%	Replanning budget	part of obj. value
Vehicle capacity	100	Maximum frequency	5
Cost of freq. replanning	200	Cost of line replanning	1000

Table 16: Relative computational effort of various settings

Plot 52 shows the calculation time differences for various solvers and settings. Here, the solvers among each other are not compared, but the performance of the various settings when employed by different solvers. Four different parameter sets were tested for all solvers, procedures, and functions and then the average calculation time was taken to compare the results. Compared to the standard setting (aggregated subtour elimination 4.16.2, quadratic frequency determination 4.13.2, and routing aggregation 4.11), the waiver of subtour elimination is not able to speed up the process drastically. For the Stochastic Programs implementations, the process is between 13% and 22% faster, which is mainly explainable by the smaller problem size, which has especially big implications for the Stochastic Programs implementations. For the other procedures, it seems that the more difficult solving process and the reduction of possibilities are balancing each other. However, the subtour aggregation is crucial for an acceptable calculation time. Without this option, up to 12 times longer optimization processes have to be taken into account, which would be almost impossible for the biggest networks.

Figure 52: Relative computational effort of various settings

The same holds for the subtour aggregation. Here the performance collapse is even stronger with up to 17 times longer calculation times. The Stochastic Programs solvers aren't even able to solve the problem after hours of calculations. The most interesting function in terms of calculation time is the frequency determination. According to the Gurobi manual (Gurobi Optimization 2024) quadratic problems are generally harder to solve compared to linear problems. Therefore two options were implemented to compare the performance, using linearization. Interestingly quadratic frequency determination takes half the time for the integrated procedure, whereas for the separated procedures, the calculation times are similar. Therefore all other calculations were made using the quadratic frequency determination.

6 Discussion

6.1 The Significance of the Composition of the Objective Value Function

The objective value function plays a crucial role in two-stage line planning. The fact, that it is composed of three different aspects makes the chosen implementation to a multi-objective problem. This could be problematic, as travel time costs affect passengers, whereas line operation costs affect the operator, and replanning costs probably affect in a way both parties. This means, that the algorithm searches for an optimal line plan, which works well for both, but which is generally not the best for both stakeholders and not even the best for one. If only travel time cost were integrated into the objective value function, enough capacity would be provided to transport each passenger on the most direct path. On the other hand, if the algorithm doesn't care about travel time cost, only the minimum needed network would be provided, with possibly long deviations for the passengers. One approach would be to use budgets for one of the two aspects. The main advantage would consist of the separation of two cost structures, which doesn't affect the same party. Another advantage could be that line operators indeed have a fixed budget for their operations, which can be fully used to provide optimal travel time costs. However, a fixed line operation budget would be much more difficult when doing parameter comparison. It remains unclear, what a good line cost budget would be and how it is determined. Being too tight leads to high costs for travelers or even a non-solvable problem. Too loose budgets on the other side are extremely resource-intensive. Another approach could be to use only line operation costs as objective value and to impose a penalty if the travel time costs are getting longer compared to an undisturbed line plan, accounting for lost ticket income, if passengers decide not to use the network anymore if longer travel times apply.

6.1.1 Replanning Costs as Part of the Objective Value

The integration of replanning costs is adding a new level of complexity. These costs are crucial for the result of two-stage line planning problems, for example, seen here 5.4. In reality, replanning costs would account for the expenses of the operator to adapt their service, but also for passengers who have to search new paths. But it would be also possible to argue, that these costs are already integrated into the line operation costs for the operator if deviated lines have longer operation times and therefore higher operation costs. The same is valid for the travel time costs. Nevertheless, the two-stage line planning problem needs some sort of measure to tighten the first-stage line plan to the second-stage line plans. Otherwise, the two-stage problem is reduced to several one-stage line planning problems with no relation between each other. This is mirrored in the replanning cost subsection, where it is very easy to see, what is happening if no replanning costs apply. Moreover, the height of replanning cost determines mainly the

necessity of integrated or separated procedures. As long as replanning costs are negligible in relation to the other two cost blocks, the integrated procedure is not advantageous. As soon as replanning costs have a noticeable influence on the total cost (starting at around 10% of total costs, as may be seen in 5.4), the differences start to be relevant and the user has to decide if an integrated procedure is needed or not. As the integrated procedure takes on average two to five longer compared to the separated approach, this decision affects the solvable problem size. The optimal would be to solve the same problem using both procedures and to compare the results.

6.2 Networks, Scenarios, and the Line Pool

The choice of the network size, the number and complexity of the scenarios as well as the number of lines in the line pool affects mainly the calculation time. But there are also implications for the resulting line plans and the solvability, such as the Sioux Falls network with 22 nodes, which is solvable only with 18 lines, whereas all other network sizes are solvable with at least 12 lines. Another interesting example is the line pool for the subsection 5.4. There the orange-brown line was adapted to serve node 16 instead of 10 to make the differences between the separated and integrated approach visible, which may be seen here 35. Without prior adaptation, node 16 would be served only by lines either affected in the first or second scenario. This would make it impossible to serve the whole network with one line plan, which works for both scenarios and the first stage.

Needless to say, the found line plans depend fully on the network, the scenarios, and the given line pool. Therefore it is very difficult to make general conclusions, as all results are highly dependent on the parameter set and the general conditions. However, it seems clear, that a lot of different scenarios with complex interruptions, which affect many lines, are increasing the calculation time, whereas peripheral restrictions, small networks, small line pools, and few scenarios decrease the calculation time. The objective value function on the other side increases with bigger networks but decreases with bigger line pools. More scenarios don't affect the objective value function, as all scenarios are always weighted to a total of 100%. Scenarios with more restrictions increase the objective value, as replanning costs are higher, and longer routes for lines and passengers have to be taken into account. On the other hand, undisturbed scenarios in the second stage reduce the total costs and lead to smaller differences between the integrated and separated procedures.

6.3 Optimality Gap

The estimated calculation time to reach optimality often requires setting an optimality gap bigger than zero to achieve an acceptable calculation time. This comes with some problems. The first one is connected with the separated procedure. As the first stage is a comparably easy problem to solve and therefore very fast, optimization gaps above zero lead to too early

termination before the best result is known, even if it would have taken only a few more seconds to find the best result. To deal with this problem, the first stage solver optimizes always to zero. Noticing this problem very late resulted in a lot of effort to run all separated procedures one more time. The first-stage line plans, which were always not optimal, but 1% to 2% worse than expected led to a concise difference between the integrated and separated procedure. After repeating the tests, this difference is often much less clear. The second problem was more difficult to solve, but at least it comparably affected both procedures. The estimated calculation time is not easy to predict. Remembering figure 50, where the incumbent solution doesn't change for a long time, whereas the lower bound is gradually tightened. It seems, that no better solution is found within an acceptable time and it seems as well, that most of the time is used to prove that the incumbent solution is good or even optimal. After numerous tests, the same behavior is observed over and over. To reduce the long calculation times, either the gap may be raised or a time limit set. If the gap is set too early, not the best solution is found and the optimization algorithm terminates within minutes. These results may lead to wrong assumptions. If the gap however is set too low, it may take hours to even reach the gap, whereas most of the time, the incumbent doesn't change. Therefore a combination of a relatively tight time limit in combination with an optimization gap of 0 seems a promising strategy to deal with both problems. However, this approach could be problematic when comparing the integrated with the separated procedure, as the separated procedure is often faster compared with the integrated procedure and therefore able to find the best solution within the time frame, whereas the integrated procedure only found a medium solution within the time frame.

6.4 Robustness in Two-Stage Line Planning

Robustness in two-stage optimization is an important concept. Starting with the difference between one-stage and two-stage optimization models. One-stage line plans may be built with the intention, that they are more robust to potential disruptions. This may include adding redundancy by providing different paths to the same destination, not using paths that are susceptible to disruptions, or other measures.

When separating the first-stage and second-stage optimization runs, the first-stage optimization run is not able to take into account future disruptions. Therefore the second stage optimization run has to adapt the first stage line plan in order not to violate the new restrictions. This behaviour seems similar to the recovery robustness, described by Goerigk et al. 2016. The adaptations are made using a set of replanning strategies: travel path adaptations, line frequency adaptations, and line path adaptations. The cost allocation to the replanning strategies leads to a set of second-stage line plans, which are more similar to the first-stage line plan compared to optimization runs without replanning costs. If the first and second stage are solved together, the disturbances of the second stage directly influence the first-stage line plan. The goal is to determine a first-stage line plan, which allows for cost-efficient adaptations to the second-stage

line plans. This is a crucial difference to the separated-solving procedure. In contrast to the separated procedure, no recovery is needed, but a planned adjustment of the second-stage line plan. Therefore the concept of adjustable robustness fits better. Additionally, the first-stage line plan is robust itself, when considering possible future infrastructure restrictions.

One special case is the strict robustness. When applying a replanning budget of zero or when adding the replanning costs to the objective value and increasing the replanning costs significantly above the total travel time and line operation costs (and if no replanning is used), the first and second-stage line plans are identical if a feasible solution exists. The first stage line plan, therefore, is the best line plan, which can deal with all restrictions. This is a classic case of strict robustness if only infrastructure disturbances are considered to be uncertain. A concrete example in subsection 5.4 shows, that the total costs of a strict robust line plan are 58% higher compared to optimal fitting line plans for each scenario.

7 Conclusion

RQ 1: How can stochastic mathematical optimization be used in the context of an LPP? After conducting all test series and analyzing the results, two-stage optimization for the line planning problem under infrastructure restrictions is a powerful tool to generate robust line plans. The chosen implementation allows to adapt a lot of parameters and to choose different algorithms to solve the line planning problem for artificial and real-life networks. The parameter choice as well as the calibration of the parameters to real-life values remain a major challenge. Especially the determination of the replanning cost is difficult, as it is hard to find a real-world equivalence with a clear associated cost.

RQ 2: What performance can stochastic mathematical optimization achieve when solving an integrated two-stage LPP compared to a separated two-stage LPP? The achievable performance is highly dependent on the size of the network and the line pool, the parameter set, and the solving technique. The solving time ranges from seconds for networks with ten nodes to hours for networks with 24 nodes. Comparing the integrated and separated approach, the calculation time of the integrated approach is on average two to five times longer. The objective value for the integrated procedure on the other side is always smaller or at least has the same height as the objective value of the separated approach. However, if the solving time is restricted, the separated procedure may find better solutions within the same time frame, outperforming the integrated procedure. The quantitative difference is highly dependent on the parameter choice, especially the flexibility and redundancy of the network, providing enough lines in the line pool as well as most importantly the value of the replanning cost. Generally speaking the higher the replanning cost and the more flexible the network is, the higher the difference. However, the advantages of an integrated procedure are always dependent on the individual case.

RQ 3: How do model parameters influence the solution and the performance of the two-stage LPP? The parameters are highly influential for the calculation time. Comprehensive tests showed, that the network size, the line pool size, and the procedure all are highly significant for the calculation time. More restricted circumstances such as a tight replanning budget, high replanning cost, no or very limited replanning possibilities, and a small number of scenarios reduce the calculation time. The large amount of parameters however makes it difficult to make exact predictions for the estimated calculation time in advance. The optimization settings also play a crucial role. The activated routing aggregation and subtour aggregation are extremely important for a short calculation time, as both may reduce the time by a factor of up to 20. In contrast to that, a quadratic or linear frequency determination plays a subordinate role. Subtour elimination is important for a reasonable result but doesn't affect the calculation times in a bad way. The advanced solving algorithms such as progressive

hedging and the l-shaped method performed worse than expected. The progressive hedging algorithm was always slower and sometimes didn't find the optimal result, which was found by the simple solvers within a shorter time. The l-shaped solver was not even able to reduce the gap below 75% for a seven-node network. The iterative first and second-stage optimization method showed some promising results but need further investigation.

RQ 4: Which solution results from the use of stochastic mathematical optimization in the context of an LPP for networks? Two-stage stochastic optimization produces comprehensible, reproducible, and good first- and second-stage line plans. These line plans may be used as a template for real line plans. Using numerous benchmarks such as operation, travel, and replanning costs and the utilization rates for all stages and scenarios individually it is possible to determine the effects of the line plan for real-life operations.

RQ 5: How robust to disturbances are the line plans found by the two-stage optimization? Two-stage optimization produces robust results, depending on the procedure they are either similar to the concept of recovery robustness for the separated procedure or adjustable robustness for the integrated procedure. If the line plan is equal for all stages and scenarios, the line plan is strictly robust.

8 Outlook

The code provided allows for further research and extensions in functionality. Several topics may be examined to push the research of two-stage line planning with uncertain infrastructure even further. The probably most important topic is the application of advanced algorithms such as a self-implemented l-shaped solver or a Lagrangian relaxation and to test, if these algorithms have advantages over the application of simple, commercial solvers and Stochastic Programs. It would be also interesting to implement some sort of additional heuristics such as a system split, which means, that passenger routing is made first and then the line plan is adapted afterward. This could potentially be good for the performance as well, but the worsening quality has to be considered as well.

Unfortunately, the line optimization algorithm within optimization doesn't prove to be efficient enough to be employed for medium-sized networks. As a compromise a semi-fixed optimization algorithm with fixed start and end points and a maximal and minimal line length could be implemented. Using this approach, the quality of the line plan could be improved significantly without reducing the computational performance as much as with the free line optimization approach.

The optimization algorithm sometimes tends to use as many different lines as possible to reach optimal coverage and utilization. This means generally low frequencies, which could have a bad influence on the ridership in practice. To incentivize higher frequencies, a penalty for the first use of a line may be imposed. To incentivize higher frequencies. Speaking of lines, direct connections don't have any advantage to changes at stations. To add incentives for direct connections, a line-changing fee has to be imposed. The problem is, however, that each passenger has to be assigned to a set of lines, which would be computationally very demanding. However, it would be very interesting to see the differences in terms of objective value and computational performance.

9 Appendix

9.1 Declaration of the use of generative AI

While working on this thesis, for some tasks generative AI came into operation. Specifically general coding tasks were outsourced to AI such as generating the code for plots, reading and computing the necessary data for the optimization process or to better understand error messages. Generative AI was also used to produce Latex code, for example, to generate tables or show graphics and for minor translation tasks. Generative AI was explicitly not used to write all code concerning the optimization process and to write this report and the paper.

9.2 List of Abbreviations

9.2.1 Parameters

Abbreviation and value range	Name
$c \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	capacity per vehicle
$k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	number of allowed lines
$m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	maximum frequency per line
$w \in \mathbb{R}$	weight of line operating cost
$d \in \mathbb{R}$	frequency replanning cost
$e \in \mathbb{R}$	line replanning cost
$o \in \mathbb{R}$	passenger path replanning cost
$b \in \mathbb{R}$	replanning budget

Table 17: Abbreviations and their explanations (parameters)

9.2.2 Constants

Abbreviation and value range	Name
$n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$	number of nodes
$\xi \in \mathbb{R} \cap \{0, 1\}^S$	probability of each scenario
$T \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	travel cost matrix
$R \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	line cost matrix
$P \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{V \times V}$	passenger origin destination list
$I \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	infrastructure capacity matrix
$I^{s2,base} \in \{0, 1\}^{V \times V}$	reduced infrastructure capacity for the second stage
$G \in \{0, 1\}^{V \times V \times l}$	predefined line matrix
$E \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, e]^k$	line group assignment list
$M = 1000$	Big M variable

Table 18: Abbreviations and their explanations (constants)

9.2.3 Variables

Abbreviation and value range	Name
$F \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V \times V}$	flow variable
$F^{agg} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	aggregated flow variable
$L \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^{k \times V \times V}$	line variable
$L^{bin} \in \{0, 1\}^{k \times V \times V}$	binary line variable
$L^{agg} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V}$	aggregated line variable
$O \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{k \times V}$	line origin destination variable
$ O \in \{0, 1\}^{k \times V}$	absolute line origin destination variable
$Q \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [0, m]^k$	line frequency variable
$Q^{group} \in \mathbb{E} \cap [0, m]^e$	line group frequency variable
$Q^{bin} \in \{0, 1\}^{k \times m}$	binary line frequency variable
$C \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{k \times V \times V}$	secondary line variable
$D \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{k \times V \times V}$	secondary line origin destination variable
$W \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^k$	line rerouting determination variable
$\Delta L \in \mathbb{Z}^{k \times V \times V}$	line difference variable
$ \Delta L \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{k \times V \times V}$	absolute line difference variable
$\Delta Q \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [-m, m]^k$	frequency difference variable
$ \Delta Q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \cap [0, m]^k$	absolute frequency difference variable
$\Delta F \in \mathbb{Z}^{V \times V \times V}$	passenger path difference variable
$ \Delta F \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{V \times V \times V}$	absolute passenger path difference variable

Table 19: Abbreviations and their explanations (variables) no repetition of variable

9.2.4 Sets

Abbreviation and value range	Name
V	set of stations
K	set of lines
S	set of scenarios

Table 20: Abbreviations and their explanations (indexes)

9.2.5 Indices

Abbreviation and value range	Name
$i \in V$	index for nodes
$j \in V$	index for nodes
$h \in V$	index for origin destination pairs
$l \in k$	index for lines
$f \in \mathbb{Z} \cap [1, m]$	index for frequencies
$s \in S$	index for scenarios

Table 21: Abbreviations and their explanations (indexes)

References

- Asghari, Mohammad, Amir M Fathollahi-Fard, S M J Mirzapour Al-e-hashem, and Maxim A Dulebenets (2022). “Transformation and Linearization Techniques in Optimization: A State-of-the-Art Survey”. In: *Mathematics* 10.2. ISSN: 2227-7390. DOI: 10.3390/math10020283. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/10/2/283>.
- Bashiri, Mahdi, Erfaneh Nikzad, Andrew Eberhard, John Hearne, and Fabricio Oliveira (2021). “A two stage stochastic programming for asset protection routing and a solution algorithm based on the Progressive Hedging algorithm”. In: *Omega* 104, p. 102480. ISSN: 0305-0483. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2021.102480>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030504832100089X>.
- Bessas, Apostolos, Spyros Kontogiannis, and Christos Zaroliagis (2011). “Robust Line Planning in Case of Multiple Pools and Disruptions”. In: *Theory and Practice of Algorithms in (Computer) Systems*. Ed. by Alberto Marchetti-Spaccamela and Michael Segal. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 33–44. ISBN: 978-3-642-19754-3.
- Biel, Martin and Mikael Johansson (2022). “Efficient stochastic programming in Julia”. In: *INFORMS Journal on Computing*.
- Borndörfer, Ralf, Martin Grötschel, and Marc Pfetsch (Feb. 2007). “A Column-Generation Approach to Line Planning in Public Transport”. In: *Transportation Science* 41, pp. 123–132. DOI: 10.1287/trsc.1060.0161.
- Borndörfer, Ralf, Martin Grötschel, and Marc E Pfetsch (2008). “Models for Line Planning in Public Transport”. In: *Computer-aided Systems in Public Transport*. Ed. by Mark Hickman, Pitu Mirchandani, and Stefan Voß. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 363–378. ISBN: 978-3-540-73312-6.
- Buchanan, Mark (2019). “The benefits of public transport”. In: *Nature Physics* 15.9, p. 876. ISSN: 1745-2481. DOI: 10.1038/s41567-019-0656-8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-019-0656-8>.
- Bussieck, Michael (1998). “Optimal Lines in Public Rail Transport”. PhD thesis. Braunschweig: Technische Universität Braunschweig.
- Dienst H (1978). “Linienplanung im spurgeführten Personenverkehr mit Hilfe eines heuristischen Verfahrens.” PhD thesis. Braunschweig: Technische Universität Braunschweig.
- Federal office for transport (2015). *Dokumentation Planungsgrundlagen STEP Ausbauschrift 2030*. Tech. rep. Bern: Bundesamt für Verkehr, p. 5.
- Gattermann, Philine, Jonas Harbering, and Anita Schöbel (2017). “Line pool generation”. In: *Public Transport* 9.1, pp. 7–32. ISSN: 1613-7159. DOI: 10.1007/s12469-016-0127-x. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12469-016-0127-x>.
- Gilrein, Erica J, Thomaz M Carvalhaes, Samuel A Markolf, Mikhail V Chester, Braden R Allenby, and Margaret Garcia (July 2021). “Concepts and practices for transforming infrastructure from rigid to adaptable”. In: *Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure* 6.3-4,

- pp. 213–234. ISSN: 2378-9689. DOI: 10.1080/23789689.2019.1599608. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23789689.2019.1599608>.
- Goerigk, Marc and Anita Schöbel (2016). “Algorithm Engineering in Robust Optimization”. In: *Algorithm Engineering: Selected Results and Surveys*. Ed. by Lasse Kliemann and Peter Sanders. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 245–279. ISBN: 978-3-319-49487-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-49487-6_{_}8. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49487-6_8.
- Grass, Emilia, Kathrin Fischer, and Antonia Rams (2020). “An accelerated L-shaped method for solving two-stage stochastic programs in disaster management”. In: *Annals of Operations Research* 284.2, pp. 557–582. ISSN: 1572-9338. DOI: 10.1007/s10479-018-2880-5. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-018-2880-5>.
- Gurobi Optimization, LLC (2024). *Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual*.
- Hassannayebi, Erfan, Seyed Hessameddin Zegordi, Mohammad Reza Amin-Naseri, and Masoud Yaghini (2017). “Train timetabling at rapid rail transit lines: a robust multi-objective stochastic programming approach”. In: *Operational Research* 17.2, pp. 435–477. ISSN: 1866-1505. DOI: 10.1007/s12351-016-0232-2. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12351-016-0232-2>.
- Huangfu, Q. and J. A. J. Hall (2018). “Parallelizing the dual revised simplex method”. In: *Mathematical Programming Computation* 10.1, pp. 119–142.
- Infanger, Gerd (2011). *Stochastic programming*. Springer.
- Liebchen, Christian (2008). *Linien-, Fahrplan-, Umlauf- und Dienstplanoptimierung: Wie weit können diese bereits integriert werden?* Tech. rep. Berlin: Heureka.
- Lin, Dung-Ying and Yu-Hsiung Ku (2014). “An implicit enumeration algorithm for the passenger service planning problem: Application to the Taiwan Railways Administration line”. In: *European Journal of Operational Research* 238.3, pp. 863–875. ISSN: 0377-2217. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2014.04.025>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0377221714003518>.
- Liu, Renming, Shukai Li, and Lixing Yang (2020). “Collaborative optimization for metro train scheduling and train connections combined with passenger flow control strategy”. In: *Omega* 90, p. 101990. ISSN: 0305-0483. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2018.10.020>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305048318301385>.
- Lubin, Miles, Oscar Dowson, Joaquim Dias Garci, Joey Huchette, Beno Legat, and Juan Pablo Vielma (2023). “JuMP 1.0: Recent improvements to a modeling language for mathematical optimization”. In: *Mathematical Programming Computation*. DOI: 10.1007/s12532-023-00239-3.
- Marín, A and B Pelegrín (1999). “Applying Lagrangian relaxation to the resolution of two-stage location problems”. In: *Annals of Operations Research* 86.0, pp. 179–198. ISSN: 1572-9338. DOI: 10.1023/A:1018998500803. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018998500803>.

- Marín, Ángel, Juan A Mesa, and Federico Perea (2009). “Integrating Robust Railway Network Design and Line Planning under Failures”. In: *Robust and Online Large-Scale Optimization: Models and Techniques for Transportation Systems*. Ed. by Ravindra K Ahuja, Rolf H Möhring, and Christos D Zaroliagis. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 273–292. ISBN: 978-3-642-05465-5. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-05465-5_{_}11. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-05465-5_11.
- Michel, S and B Chidlovskii (2016). “Stochastic optimization of public transport schedules to reduce transfer waiting times”. In: *2016 IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)*, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/ISC2.2016.7580860.
- Mulvey, John M, Robert J Vanderbei, and Stavros A Zenios (Apr. 1995). “Robust Optimization of Large-Scale Systems”. In: *Operations Research* 43.2, pp. 264–281. ISSN: 0030-364X. DOI: 10.1287/opre.43.2.264. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.43.2.264>.
- Naumann, Marc, Leena Suhl, and Stefan Kramkowski (2011). “A stochastic programming approach for robust vehicle scheduling in public bus transport”. In: *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 20, pp. 826–835. ISSN: 1877-0428. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.08.091>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042811014716>.
- Oencan, Temel, I Kuban Altinel, and Gilbert Laporte (2009). “A comparative analysis of several asymmetric traveling salesman problem formulations”. In: *Computers & Operations Research* 36.3, pp. 637–654. ISSN: 0305-0548. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2007.11.008>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305054807002468>.
- Oki, Eiji (2012). “GLPK (GNU Linear Programming Kit)”. In: URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:63578694>.
- Pu, Song and Shuguang Zhan (2021). “Two-stage robust railway line-planning approach with passenger demand uncertainty”. In: *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 152, p. 102372. ISSN: 1366-5545. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2021.102372>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S136655452100140X>.
- Pykes, Kurtis (Dec. 2022). *Julia vs Python - Which Should You Learn?*
- Reinhardt, Winfried (2012). “Angebotsplanung im ÖPNV”. In: *Öffentlicher Personennahverkehr: Technik – rechtliche und betriebswirtschaftliche Grundlagen*. Ed. by Winfried Reinhardt. Wiesbaden: Vieweg+Teubner Verlag, pp. 437–484. ISBN: 978-3-8348-8234-9. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-8348-8234-9_{_}7. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8348-8234-9_7.
- Rockafellar, R T and Roger J.-B. Wets (Feb. 1991). “Scenarios and Policy Aggregation in Optimization Under Uncertainty”. In: *Mathematics of Operations Research* 16.1, pp. 119–147. ISSN: 0364-765X. DOI: 10.1287/moor.16.1.119. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1287/moor.16.1.119>.

- Schnieder, Lars (2015). “Netzplanung”. In: *Betriebsplanung im öffentlichen Personennahverkehr: Ziele, Methoden, Konzepte*. Ed. by Lars Schnieder. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 21–43. ISBN: 978-3-662-46456-4. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-46456-4_2. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-46456-4_2.
- Schöbel, Anita (2012). “Line planning in public transportation: models and methods”. In: *OR Spectrum* 34.3, pp. 491–510. ISSN: 1436-6304. DOI: 10.1007/s00291-011-0251-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00291-011-0251-6>.
- Schöbel, Anita and Alexander Schiewe (Aug. 2022). *Lintim - An integrated environment for mathematical public transport optimization*. Tech. rep. Kaiserslautern: Fraunhofer ITWM Kaiserslautern.
- Shapiro, Alexander and A Philpott (Apr. 2007). *A tutorial on stochastic programming*.
- SMA and Partner, Intraplan Consult, Via Consultion & Development, and TTS Trimode Transport Solutions (2022). *Abschlussbericht Deutschlandtakt*. Tech. rep. Berlin: Bundesministeriums für Digitales und Verkehr.
- Sun, Ran and Yueyue Fan (2024). “Stochastic OD demand estimation using stochastic programming”. In: *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* 183, p. 102943. ISSN: 0191-2615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2024.102943>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0191261524000675>.
- Unterberger, Stefan and Ambra Toletti (2022). *Digitalisierung in der Fahrplanplanung*. Tech. rep. Bern: SBB.
- Wallace, Stein W. and William T. Ziemba (2005). *Applications of stochastic programming*. Philadelphia: Society for Industrial, Applied Mathematics, and the Mathematical Programming Society.